

ER4STEM CURRICULUM

[Deliverable 2.4]

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ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE, PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a final report on the complete ER4STEM Generic Curriculum as developed by the ER4STEM project partners during the ER4STEM project implementation period. In this deliverable, we provide an overview of the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum on educational robotics, where we connect the elements and the processes, which the ER4STEM team applied to deliver Educational Robotics Workshops (henceforth: ERWs). This report is intended to be used by the ER4STEM target groups, including but not limited to **teachers, educators, researchers and academia, as reference material for the design, adaptation, and organization of ERWs following the ER4STEM approach**. The quantitative data in this deliverable is based on the information reported through the workshop information forms, provided by each partner in Y1, Y2 and Y3 of the project.

1.2 RELATIONSHIP TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

A draft idea of the ER4STEM framework, the criteria for selecting good practices and the Activity Plan template were initially presented in D1.1 Best Practice & Requirements and D4.1 First Version of the Activity Plans. These elements correlate with D1.2 ER4STEM Framework First Structure and Roadmap 2nd Year and D4.2 Operational Release of Activity Plans.

The educational robotics workshops run alongside the implementation of the D6.2 Evaluation Tool Kit. Data handling follows the data structure defined in D8.1 Data Management Plan. Conclusions in D6.3 Evaluation and Analysis of 1st Project Year and D6.4 Evaluation and Analysis of 2nd Project Year were taken into account when the ERWs implementation process was updated. We work in cooperation with WP6 in order to take into account the draft conclusions from D6.5 Evaluation and Analysis of 3rd Project Year, which was under development in parallel with this report. The Generic Curriculum on educational robotics, functions as a mediating instrument between the ER4STEM Framework (WP1) and the implementation of ERWs (WP2), mapping Activity Plans developed in WP4, in alignment to the evaluation results from the workshops (WP6).

The structure of this report follows the already established structure and guidelines in D2.3 Workshop Report 3rd Year. This report summarises, and more importantly systematises the ideas and content that were developed during the 35 months of the project's execution. The ideas and content were described in details in D2.1 Workshop Report 1st Year; D2.2 Workshop Report 2nd Year; D2.3 Workshop Report 3rd Year.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THIS DOCUMENT

Section 2 Background for the Development of the Generic Educational Robotics Curriculum describes the overall concepts, methodology and architecture of the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum. Section 3 Generic Curriculum: Context describes the Context of ER4STEM Generic Curriculum on a macro level and its interrelation with the ER4STEM Framework and presents a baseline for the Generic Curriculum Path Template. Section 4 Generic Curriculum: Content informs on the content of the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum on a meso level as well as it provides a link to the content of the ERWs Activity Plans. Section 5 Generic Curriculum: Process provides a process description of how the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum and ERWs could be used by relevant stakeholders. Section 6 ER4STEM Workshops Report provides summary of aggregated quantitative data of all ER4STEM ERWs executed within the project period. Section 7 Conclusion / Outlook provides a summary of the conclusions and outlooks related to the

ER4STEM Generic Curriculum. APPENDIX 1 QUANTITATIVE DATA FROM THE ERWS BASED ON THE WORKSHOP INFORMATION FORMS provides in a table format the key characteristics of the ERWs completed throughout the entire project implementation period.

2 BACKGROUND FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GENERIC EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS CURRICULUM

TERMS INTRODUCED IN THIS CHAPTER:

- **Generic Curriculum Path:** A tool introduced under the ER4STEM project to address desired learning outcomes through a set of use cases. A Generic Curriculum Path consists of a set of educational robotics workshops or single activities within the workshops Activity Plans, which are suitable for a given context, students, specific objectives and prior knowledge. A Generic Curriculum Path is designed to be further modified by the educator to fit their specific learning context.
- **Generic Curriculum Map:** The curriculum map is the contextual visualization of educational robotics learning opportunities, as organized content into a set of use cases and contexts, revolving around desired learning outcomes. It is a part of the context layer of the generic educational robotics curriculum under the ER4STEM project.
- **Generic Curriculum Path Template:** As is the Activity Plan Template, the Generic Curriculum Path Template is a design tool of a generic nature. The Generic Curriculum Path Template facilitates different stakeholders to design Generic Curriculum Paths for different robotics toolkits, containing various educational robotics Activity Plans and addressing various STEM domains. This template provides a simple structure serving as the backbone for the formulation of the use cases, or the logic, behind a Generic Curriculum Path and is the common element between a set of Activity Plans.
- **Generic Curriculum Architecture:** The ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Architecture represents the structure of all elements comprising the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum on educational robotics. The ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Architecture organizes the Generic Curriculum elements in three levels - macro, meso and micro levels, all of which are further broken down into context, content and process levels.
- **Generic Process:** The Generic Process aims to provide a clear picture to researchers and teachers on the key steps that were planned and executed within the ER4STEM project for the implementation of educational robotics workshops. The final version of the Generic Process presented within the current deliverable, serves as reference to teachers, educators, researchers and other relevant stakeholders who would like to apply educational robotics as a tool to maintain student's curiosity in the STEM subjects, but also to provide them with opportunities to develop the so needed 21st century skills.

2.1 CONCRETIZING THE CONCEPT OF A GENERIC CURRICULUM FOR EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS

Work Package 2, among its other goals, is expected to deliver a Generic Curriculum on educational robotics, functioning as a mediating instrument between the ER4STEM Framework (WP1) and the implementation of ERWs (WP2), mapping Activity Plans developed in WP4, in alignment to the evaluation results from the workshops (WP6).

In an attempt to provide a definition of what a curriculum is, we encountered statements declaring that such a definition is difficult to be given. The question of “**what a curriculum is**” is in its nature, a matter of profound philosophical discussion, as it yet revolves around the concept of knowledge and notably, of what is of importance to be learned for the individual within the context of the society in which they function [1]. Thus, the answer to this question has to be in alignment with theories about values, ideas and priorities. Under those circumstances, the topic of **Generic Curriculum for educational robotics** further becomes even more complex, if we consider two specific characteristics of Educational Robotics (ER): a) they are in fact, innovative technology, the integration of which dictates to take into account best practices and common approaches for integrating digital technologies in education; and b) this integration has to take place in formal (school) and non-formal settings (competitions, science centers, conferences etc.)

To solve this problem, we started off with the rather simplified definition of curriculum offered by Walker [1]: “*A curriculum is a particular way of ordering content and purposes for teaching and learning in schools[...] offering a common foundation of essential knowledge and skill*” [pp.4]. Correspondingly, when discussing **curriculum for robotics**, we also have to reflect on its nature as a scientific domain: Robotics could be considered a subject matter as well as a domain for contextualized learning of other subject matters [2], chiefly the STE(A)M related ones. The latter is also related to the approaches for integrating digital technologies in education. Specifically, Wang and Woo [3] identify three levels of ICT integration in the classroom: a) **micro level**, where integration of ICT involves a specific lesson, aiming to support student learning about specific concepts b) **meso level**, where integration involves a specific topic or use case and c) **macro level**, where integration of ICT happens at the level of a course.

The Generic Curriculum developed under the ER4STEM project reflects on the **meso** and **macro levels**, with respectively its context and content levels, while the micro level of ICT integration is targeted by the ER4STEM project through the separate workshop Activity Plans. In order to do that, two concepts were introduced to the development of the curriculum by the implementation team: 1) **Generic Curriculum Paths** and 2) **Generic Curriculum Map**, which are presented in detail in sections 3 and 4 of this deliverable, respectively. These elements were visualized in a separate section of the ER4STEM Repository (repository.er4stem.com) in order to facilitate the navigation and the understanding around the educational robotics Activity Plans, included within the repository.

Overall, **a the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum integrates knowledge about context, content and process for the implementation of educational robotics activities on macro, meso and micro levels.** (See Table 1 ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Architecture).

The **ER4STEM Generic Curriculum** on educational robotics is a structured **methodology** and a **tool** to navigate through **educational robotics activities** (as both educational approach and content), developed and applied by all partners. The ER4STEM Generic Curriculum is based on the practical implementation of the specific content developed by each partner for the educational robotics workshops implemented under the ER4STEM project. The practical foundations of the Generic Curriculum are illustrated within the current deliverable.

This Generic Curriculum is designed to support and facilitate the dissemination of good practices, related to the field of educational robotics activities, in Europe and beyond. The curriculum developed under the ER4STEM project is intended to serve educators, researchers and other relevant stakeholders in the field of educational robotics, to design, develop, adapt and/or implement their own educational activities and initiatives while navigating them through a structured representation of the activities, developed and maintained under the ER4STEM project.

Our aim is that through this curriculum, we could share our experience and expertise, so that others could benefit from the ER4STEM project's best practices and could further develop and apply them for their educational or project purposes.

2.2 THE LANDSCAPE OF A CURRICULUM FOR EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS

In D1.1 Best Practice and Requirements, the ER4STEM project team has identified a set of good practices among which there is a reference to curricula developed for ER. The basic characteristics we identified in these curricula are the following:

- They are organized according to the technology they employ (e.g. in Robotics Academy of Carnegie Mellon University there is a curriculum for Lego Mindstorms, VEX IQ Microcontroller, Virtual Brick, etc.);
- They address broad age groups focusing mainly on middle and high school. However, there are also curricula addressing elementary school students (e.g. squeakland ¹);
- Non-formal learning situations like robotics camps are addressed separately from formal learning situations. However, there are cases where preparation for contests is part of the curriculum designed for schools, which is addressed in a separate section;
- The learning activities introduced are connected to standards and formal curricula. Thus, it appears that the majority of the curricula address the *meso level*, previously introduced;
- The learning objectives focus on programming and STEM. In many cases, learning objectives also include argumentation and language development (important seems to be the construct of design journal). Furthermore, robotics seem to offer various opportunities for practicing 21st century skills and problem solving;
- Teamwork is an important aspect of a robotics curriculum and in some cases, it is supported with relevant material. Specifically, Robotics academy of Carnegie Mellon University provides a power point presentation, which identifies the two main courses of work in Robotics² (programming and engineering) and distinguishes four roles in a group (Project Manager, Information Specialist, Communications Specialist and Material specialist);
- Few curricula have an explicit pedagogical background. An elaborate example is offered by Tufts University³ that developed a curriculum, which includes the Lego WeDo platform. Specifically, the curriculum is based upon the concept of constructionism [4] and is developed around the construct of Positive Technological Development. The philosophy of this curriculum is oriented towards positive youth development (student centered – self-actualization orientation [5]) and it consists of six positive behaviors: content creation (i.e. making and programming a robot), creativity, collaboration, communication, community building, choices of conduct (i.e. experimenting with “what if” questions). The Six Cs behaviors are illustrated in Figure 1 adopted from [6].

¹ <http://squeakland.org/showcase/everyone/index.jsp?viewBy=age>

² <https://www.cmu.edu/roboticsacademy/>

³ <http://schools.nyc.gov/NR/rdonlyres/87A27687-1007-41A4-AF8A-D33FAB423C11/0/WeDoThePlaygroundCurricGrades12.pdf>

Figure 1 The Six Cs behaviors. Adapted from Bers [5]

The ER4STEM Generic Curriculum on educational robotics employs one or more of the above-mentioned good practices, especially when considering the Activity Plans, which represent the building blocks of the Generic Curriculum.

2.3 METHODOLOGY BEHIND THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ER4STEM GENERIC CURRICULUM

Curriculum development is an endeavor with many challenges. More often than not, curricula are populated with contradicting values, orientations and interests. Problems in curriculum development are often manifested in the gaps between the intended curriculum (the described curriculum), the implemented curriculum (real life in school practice) and the attained curriculum (learner experiences and outcomes) [7]. This problem in many cases is because the process of curriculum design follows a top down direction, thus, there is a rising effort to involve teachers in the design and development process.

To overcome this problem, along with the fragmentation in the domain of robotics caused by the different personal pedagogies and technologies in the field (see also [8]), we followed a bottom up approach. Specifically, we created a curriculum starting from the Activity Plans already designed and successfully implemented by the ER4STEM team in their latest improved versions, which were available in the time of development often report, following the latest version of the Generic Process for the implementation of educational robotics activities.

During the last project year, we refined this *Generic Curriculum* based on the evaluation of the workshops, feedback from the industry, educators and other relevant stakeholders and accumulated experience. We went towards unifying the *Activity Plans* under a pedagogical approach that takes into account the affordances and the special characteristics of robotics as a scientific field and as a domain for contextualized STE(A)M learning.

The Activity Plans describe in detail (D4.1 First Version of the Activity Plans) the following key elements of the Generic Curriculum on a micro (workshop) level:

- Objectives and competencies in the Activity Plans are structured and described under the following categories:
 - Subject-related;
 - Technology use related;
 - Social and action related;
 - Argumentation and fostering of maker-culture;
- Content based on the objectives, target knowledge and skills represented in the Activity Plans as “How to” in the classroom;
- Teaching (instructional) approach and materials are represented in the Activity Plans as Learning procedures section;
- Target participants are described in the “*Students*” (target audience) section in the Activity Plans;
- Necessary resources – experts, facilities and materials are described in the “*Social orchestration*”; “*Space Info*” and “*Materials and artefacts*” sections;
- Final outputs and deliverables are described and evaluated in the “*Assessment procedure*” section of the Activity Plan.

The ethical and legal aspects regarding the collection of information from the students, the parents, the schools and teachers were considered in detail and taken into account in the assessment procedures (see D6.1 Pre-Kit for Evaluation).

Finally, the industry needs, targeted by the **ER4STEM framework**, were justified according to societal/industrial needs/demands and forecasts, were researched and taken under consideration throughout the development of the ER4STEM framework and then were introduced within the content of the Activity Plans through the workshops objectives. As an example, during the second project year, we included explicitly 21st century skills in all Activity Plans, thanks to the recommendations from the evaluation of the activities during the 1st year and the industry skills analysis and recommendations.

A final report on the industry skills analysis will be available in WP6’s deliverable D6.5 Evaluation and Analysis of 3rd Project Year.

2.4 THE ER4STEM APPROACH

Assuming *the* general definition of curriculum being the general plan for educational activities, Adams and Adams [9] define a curriculum as *everything that goes in the learners’ live such as planned and not planned interaction of pupils with educational objectives, instructional content, materials and resources used and materials and resources not used, the sequence of courses, objective, standards and interpersonal relationships.*

This definition well reflects the ER4STEM vision for formal and informal educational robotics activities for all children as well as the bottom-up approach for the Generic Curriculum design.

Following this definition and taking into account the concepts described in Section 2.1 *Concretizing the Concept of A Generic Curriculum for Educational Robotics*, the ER4STEM project correspondingly presents the ERW curriculum in three components: **context**, **content** and **process**, for all three levels of

ICT integration in the classroom. To illustrate that, we introduced the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Architecture in Table 1.

ER4STEM GENERIC CURRICULUM ARCHITECTURE			
	MACRO LEVEL	MESO LEVEL	MICRO LEVEL
CONTEXT	ER4STEM Framework WP 1 Deliverable 1.4 ER4STEM: An Operational and Conceptual Framework for Educational Robotics	Generic Curriculum Paths Template 3.2 Generic Curriculum Path Template	
CONTENT	Generic Curriculum Map Figure 4 ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map	Generic Curriculum Paths Aggregation 4.2 Generic Curriculum Paths Aggregation	Activity Plans WP4 Deliverable 4.3 Final Release of Activity Plans
PROCESS		Generic Process 5 Generic Curriculum: Process	

Table 1 ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Architecture

The logic of the Generic Curriculum architecture includes:

(a) **Context** – On a **Macro level**, the context of Generic Curriculum is the ER4STEM Framework, which defines, encompasses and analyses concepts, such as background of the target group, setting (formal, non-formal), sustainability (high level) objectives of the workshops and criteria for success. This component of the **ER4STEM Generic Curriculum** on educational robotics could be considered as a prerequisite for an adequate development of the following two components below. This makes it a paramount that those components are considered not separately but altogether as integral parts of the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum. The ER4STEM Framework is a subject of WP1’s D1.4 ER4STEM: An Operational and Conceptual Framework for Educational Robotics.

On a **Meso level**, the context of the Generic Curriculum is the Generic Curriculum Path Template (3.2 Generic Curriculum Path Template). As is the Activity Plan Template, the Generic Curriculum Path Template is a design tool of a generic nature. The Generic Curriculum Path Template facilitates different stakeholders to design Generic Curriculum Paths for different robotics toolkits, containing various educational robotics Activity Plans and addressing various STEM domains. This template provides a simple structure serving as the backbone for the formulation of the use cases, or the logic, behind a Generic Curriculum Paths and is the common element between a set of Activity Plans.

The Context component of the Generic Curriculum does not cover the Micro level of ICT integration in the classroom.

(b) **Content** – On a **Macro level**, the content of the Generic Curriculum is represented by the Generic Curriculum Map (Figure 4 ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map), which is the

contextual visualization of educational robotics learning opportunities, as organized content into a set of use cases and contexts, revolving around desired learning outcomes. It is a part of the context layer of the generic educational robotics curriculum under the ER4STEM project.

On a **Meso level**, the content of the Generic Curriculum is represented by the Generic Curriculum Paths Aggregation which presents, in a table format (4.2 Generic Curriculum Paths Aggregation), an overview of the core knowledge and skills of the Generic Curriculum Paths. It aggregates the STE(A)M knowledge, 21st century skills and targeted values, as well as the core subject-objectives of the Activity Plans, comprising a Generic Curriculum Path. It further gives an overview of the technologies, programming languages, total duration and targeted STEM domains to help an educator assess the applicability of a Generic Curriculum Path to their unique use case.

On a **Micro level**, the content of the Generic Curriculum is represented by the Activity Plans that provide information about the ERWs activity itself: teaching approach, materials, target participants, necessary resources, assessment method, final outputs and deliverables. ERWs information is structured around the learning objectives. The Activity Plans are subject of WP4's D3.3 Final Release of Activity Plans.

- (c) **Process** – On a **Meso level**, the content of the Generic Curriculum is represented by the Generic Process for the implementation of ERW, which describes the sequence of activities to initiate, prepare, deliver and complete a workshop, which could be considered as a systematic walkthrough of a successful workshop delivery.

On a **Micro level**, the content of the Generic Curriculum is represented by the “how-to” procedures described by *the Activity Plan*, including leaning and teaching procedures, related to the activity. They also provide systematic how-to as well as structured information about space, materials (incl. technological tools, manual, handouts, etc.), social orchestration, and evaluation methods and instruments. The Activity Plans are described in detail in WP4's D3.3 Final Release of Activity Plans.

The Process component of the Generic Curriculum does not cover the Micro level of ICT integration in the classroom.

To sum up, the Generic Curriculum in ER4STEM is a mediating artifact between the ER4STEM Framework (WP1) and the implementation of ERWs (WP2), integrating products developed in WP4, in alignment with the evaluation results from the workshops (WP6). The Generic Curriculum consists of: a) the theoretical constructs of the ER4STEM framework and the Generic Curriculum Path Template (context) b) the Generic Curriculum Map and the Generic Curriculum Paths Aggregation, and the Activity Plans developed by practitioners (content) and c) the Generic Process for the Implementation of ERWs, as well as the results of the evaluation of the workshops (process).

This report on the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum follows the structure of the Generic Curriculum Architecture.

3 GENERIC CURRICULUM: CONTEXT

On a **Macro level**, the context of Generic Curriculum is the ER4STEM Framework, which defines, encompasses and analyses concepts, such as background of the target group, setting (formal, non-formal), sustainability goals of the workshops and criteria for success. As the ER4STEM Framework is a subject of WP1's D1.4 ER4STEM: An Operational and Conceptual Framework for Educational Robotics this chapter briefly overviews the interoperability between those two ER4STEM elements and provides more information about how the ER4STEM Framework is applied to serve the needs of the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum and vice versa

On a **Meso level**, the context of the Generic Curriculum is the Generic Curriculum Path Template. The Generic Curriculum Path Template is a simple structure serving as the backbone for the formulation of Generic Curriculum Paths and aims at helping educators, willing to create such paths to be more explicit about the logic, behind the progression between educational robotics Activity Plans.

In this section, we provide the necessary information on how we formed the currently existing Generic Curriculum Paths and provide the structure for their future expansion.

3.1 ER4STEM FRAMEWORK INTEGRATION WITH THE ER4STEM GENERIC CURRICULUM

The ER4STEM framework is, in its essence, intended to serve as a set of mechanisms, processes and tools (e.g. Activity Plans) which would assist teachers, organizers of educational robotics activities as well as educational robotics researchers and other stakeholders to design, implement, evaluate and improve educational robotics (ER) activities. These stakeholders are identified and listed in details in D1.1. As a result of this, the framework provides processes for pedagogical activities, conferences and curriculum design. A pedagogical activity in ER4STEM is considered as an activity with specific learning outcomes and artifacts of learning. This lets the activities to be used in informal (e.g. Workshops) or formal settings (e.g. Lessons).

The need for an educational robotics framework stems out of the fact that regardless of similarities and common elements that the educational robotics learning activities might share, components of those activities might appear fragmented, especially due to the multidisciplinary nature of the field of robotics, STEM and social sciences domains alike. Moreover, stakeholders have a different background and knowledge in robotics and education that could limit their ability to create pedagogical activities with robots. Thusly, the need of a framework, effectively making evident the relations between seemingly distant activities, is required to provide a common baseline for operation with the instrumentation, data and guidelines, developed under the ER4STEM project.

The framework behind the pedagogical approaches applied, or the targeted and estimated outcomes in terms of 21st century skills cultivation, is in fact a wholesome but yet complex structure with the goal to provide generic guidelines on how to understand, create, implement, sustain and evaluate educational robotics activities within shared, public spaces, through robotics as a mediating artefact to engage and empower children to:

- Engage in collaboration;
- Provide sense of achievement;
- Develop the ability to recover from failure;

- Be part of a creative environment;
- Cultivate further interests within the domains of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM);

On a macro level, the approach underlying the ER4STEM educational robotics activities consists of four main macro steps (see Figure 2): design or adaptation, implementation, evaluation or assessment, and improvement. This aims to suggest that **all activities presented could be adapted to fit a certain context, be it pedagogical, logistical or technological**. The Framework behind the ER4STEM project also aims to guide stakeholders towards a generic process for developing and structuring their own pedagogical activities with robotics or Generic Curriculum Paths. Below, Figure 2 presents the macro process definition, as described in D1.3 Towards an Extended Definition of ER4STEM Framework.

Figure 2 ER4STEM Framework's Macro Process Definition (for more information, see D1.3 Towards an Extended Definition of ER4STEM Framework)

The first phase of the Macro Process Definition, design or adaptation, is divided into two possible steps, which represent the possibility to design an activity from scratch or adapt one from other existing activities. The Generic Curriculum on educational robotic developed under WP2 supports this initial step of the macro process, by assisting stakeholders to adapt or design their own Generic Paths through the Generic Curriculum Path Template. With the Generic Curriculum Map and the Generic Curriculum Paths Aggregation, the Generic Curriculum assists relevant stakeholders to identify use cases and activities of interest to their educational context and helps them navigate through the Activity Plans, already created by the ER4STEM project team.

The second phase of the Macro Process Definition of the Framework is the implementation phase. The implementation phase of the Macro Process Definition, as defined by the ER4STEM Framework, puts a strong focus on implementing the educational robotics activity in a way that fosters participants' interest in STEM, and implementing guidelines to inspire children's curiosity in the natural world through robotics. The Generic educational robotics Curriculum serves the goals of the implementation phase of the macro process by providing a Generic Process for the delivery of educational robotics activities (see 5 Generic Curriculum: Process).

The third phase of the Macro Process Definition is the Evaluation or Assessment phase. Within WP6, an evaluation toolkit for educational robotics activities has been developed to support the implementation by assessing the impact of the educational robotics activities, but also in order to identify limitations or possible improvements. Generic Guidelines for the improvement of educational robotics workshops are also provided by the Generic Curriculum Process (see 5 Generic Curriculum: Process).

The fourth and last phase focuses on implementing improvements to the Activity Plans based on the information derived from the implementation in real settings, reflections from the teachers, students and the designers. Through the Post-Activity Reports (provided by ER4STEM's WP4), as well as tutor observations and reflections (provided by ER4STEM's WP6), possible areas of improvement within the Activity Plans and their actual execution are identified.

Once the activity has been improved, the cycle can be repeated with further adaptation of the activity for future groups and their specific educational context, as necessary. For the last two processes, the curriculum could serve by providing generic guidelines. The process, described in detail in 5 Generic Curriculum: Process of this document, could be applied in all phases of the ER4STEM Framework's Macro Process Definition for the organization of educational robotics activities.

All of the above-mentioned Macro Process Definition phases, along with the processes relevant to each level, are supported by a glossary, which is presented in detail in WP1. The aim of the glossary is to establish a common language and align relevant stakeholders to the context of the ER4STEM project in general.

Among the core ER4STEM objectives is to study real-world societal problems as perceived by children and to relate societal changes to existing technologies and required innovations. The ER4STEM activities, as per the project proposal, are designed to empower children to define problems that influence their lives and provide them with the necessary skills to solve these (based on the principles of constructionism). One of the means to ensure that was to incorporate opportunities in the ER4STEM Framework and, through it, in the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum to develop soft-skills essential to research and industry.

Due to its multidisciplinary nature, robotics offers vast opportunities to acquire and develop **21st century skills**. Those skills are recognized by the ER4STEM project as necessary for the successful implementation of the project vision and goals. In order to achieve this sustainably, after a project partners meeting in Malta, on the onset of project year 2 and by the initiative of WP6 and WP4 with according to the industry needs research, a common ER4STEM understanding of **21st century skills** were introduced and gradually maintained.

To begin with, the ER4STEM partners agreed on a common list and understanding of the 21st century skills that should be addressed by the ER4STEM project. The list was based on "*The Framework for 21st Century Learning*"⁴, created by the P21 Partnership. This framework is a blend of knowledge, skills, expertise and literacies that students must master in order to succeed in 21st century work and life. Other enlisted 21st century learning skills include the "*ISTE Educational Technology Standards*" which is a set of standards published by the International Society for Technology in Education (ISTE) to leverage

⁴ <http://www.p21.org/our-work/p21-framework>

the use of technology in K-12 education⁵, the “7 survival skills” by Tony Wagner who identifies the most important skills needed for today’s workspace⁶, as well as the “enGauge® 21st Century Skills: Literacy in the Digital Age” report⁷, issued by the North Central Regional Educational Laboratory and the Metiri Group. In addition, the framework provides a set of good practices identified in the literature.

Last but not least, within the framework, a general understanding of 21st century skills and what they stand for is crucial. Although the set of skills targeted by a set of activities might vary, in WP1’s D1.4 ER4STEM identifies 10 values, which were selected based on ER4STEM’s aim and industry requirements. As a result, these values cover some 21st century skills (i.e. Collaboration, critical thinking, communication and critical thinking) and pedagogical aspects (i.e. Pedagogical methodologies, mixed-gender teams, differentiation, multiple entry points, evidence of learning and changing attitudes towards STEM).

Following the onset of the second project year, those 10 recommendations were embraced by the project partners and were focused upon during the design of the educational robotics activities, the plans of which now are part of the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum.

The data in Figure 3 Share of all Year 3 workshops that cover the Y2 recommendations in terms of 21st century skills presented below, is the aggregated report for all ER4STEM year 3 workshops’ engagement with the 10 recommendations. The data is taken from the workshop information sheet and is aggregated to display the inclusion of the recommended skills and characteristics to be focused during the second and the third project year.

⁵ <http://www.iste.org/standards/standards/for-students-2016>

⁶ <http://www.tonywagner.com/7-survival-skills>

⁷ <http://pict.sdsu.edu/engauge21st.pdf>

Figure 3 Share of all Year 3 workshops that cover the Y2 recommendations in terms of 21st century skills

This data was collected from the 72 workshops, conducted during year 3. The percentage in this graph represents the percentage of workshops for each of the values. For each of the recommendations, partners chose between “yes” (blue), “no” (green) and “partially” (red) to indicate the level of inclusion of the respective recommendation within the educational robotics workshops.

This table shows that despite the fact that on a macro level, the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum targets mainly STEM disciplines, on a micro level, through the Activity Plans, it focuses on the integration of 21st century skills within the activities as an important asset of the ER4STEM approach.

Last but not least, the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum with all its elements represented within the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Architecture, aims to serve educators, teachers, researchers and academia, to navigate through the ER4STEM content, in order to adapt and implement it to their unique context and desired learning outcomes.

3.2 GENERIC CURRICULUM PATH TEMPLATE

Regarding the **meso level of Generic Curriculum Architecture**, we followed a bottom-up approach based on the successful experience in delivering ERWs that were organized into STE(A)M related Generic Curriculum Paths. Thus, we analyzed how we can identify teaching and learning elements, which are connected to the nature of educational robotics: i.e. constructionist technology, multidisciplinary domain, subject matter (for instance STEAM and Business) and a domain for contextualized learning of other subject matters. To visualize that, we introduced the concept of **Generic Curriculum Paths**.

A Generic Curriculum Path, as understood under the ER4STEM project, is a tool introduced to address desired learning outcomes in STE(A)M through a set of use cases. A Generic Curriculum Path consists of a set of educational robotics workshops Activity Plans, which are suitable for a given context, students, specific objectives and prior knowledge. The Generic Curriculum Paths are of a generic nature, meaning that they are designed to be further adapted and modified by teachers, willing to implement a specific Generic Curriculum Path within their own unique learning context.

The Generic Curriculum Paths as a concept are understood as a curriculum property of a suggestive nature by presenting certain relationships between the ER4STEM Activity Plans – the **Activity Plans are connected to each other where a common desired learning outcome is identified, or a common context, such as technology or applied programming languages are taught**. However, educators who might analyze some Activity Plans are bound to find other relationships between Activity Plans, other learning outcomes that might suit their classroom needs, as well as identify other Generic Curriculum Paths that might better fit their context. Thus, the Generic Curriculum Paths are learning paths identified in correspondence to the ER4STEM values and/or are the most commonly addressed in discussions with relevant stakeholders. The Generic Curriculum Paths are meant to be taken as an opportunity, suggestion and guidelines for the educators, **not as a strict sequence of Activity Plans that has to be followed, or as a learning plan**.

Up to now, through dialogues with relevant stakeholders, we identified six Generic Curriculum Paths in total:

- 1. Technology and Engineering with LEGO:** An educator aims to teach **technology and engineering with LEGO robots**. This could be considered as a typical use case of using robots for education.
- 2. Science, Technology and Engineering (multiple technologies):** An educator aims to teach concepts of **science, technology and engineering while demonstrating various technology platforms** such as Arduino, BeeBots, Hedgehog, LEGO Mindstorms and LEGO WeDo **as well as a vast plethora of** programming languages C++, Python, LEGO Mindstorms Programming, Scratch or SNAP
- 3. Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM):** An educator aims to cover all STEM domains, Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, while also developing creativity among the students
- 4. "White-Box" Science, Technology and Engineering:** An educator aims to teach concepts in **science, technology and engineering through "white box"** platforms such as: " Arduino, Hedgehog, LEGO WeDo with a stronger focus on electronics and widely used industrial programming languages such as C++ and Python
- 5. Technology, Mathematics and Arts:** An educator aims to teach **Mathematics by using educational robotics technology**. This path covers multiple mathematical concepts and applies art and real-life problems for self-expression and teaching advanced technological principles related to programming and mathematical concepts
- 6. Technology, Engineering and Mathematics:** An educator aims to teach concepts in Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

Detailed information about the Generic Curriculum Paths and their contents is presented in 4.2 Generic Curriculum Paths Aggregation of the current deliverable. However, in order to provide a common representation of the Generic Curriculum Paths created, as well as to ensure a level of scalability,

meaning that we provide a common frame for educators to structure their own Generic Curriculum Paths, we introduce the **baseline of the Generic Curriculum Path Template**.

As is the Activity Plan Template, the Generic Curriculum Path Template is a design tool of a generic nature. The Generic Curriculum Path Template facilitates different stakeholders to design learning paths for different robotics toolkits, containing various educational robotics activity plans and addressing various STEM domains. This template provides a simple structure serving as the backbone for the formulation of the use cases, or the logic, behind a Generic Curriculum Path and is the common element between a set of Activity Plans.

A core element of the Generic Curriculum Path Template approach is instrumental theory [10] according to which the characteristics of the resources teachers select to use, shape their practice on the one hand (instrumentation) and on the other hand, the teachers' knowledge shapes the use of the resources as teachers appropriate them to fit their personal pedagogies (instrumentalization). As a result of the above, teacher designs, according to Pepin, B., Gueudet, G., & Trouche [11], are evolving or living documents - in the sense that they are continuously renewed, changed and adapted. With the Generic Curriculum and the Generic Curriculum Path Template in general, we attempt at empowering educators to create "living" educational robotics activities, by providing them a common structure to facilitate being explicit about pedagogical design.

The structure below provides high-level information about the generic logic behind the six already identified Generic Curriculum Paths by the ER4STEM project. With the Generic Curriculum Path Template, we aim at ensuring consistency, standard representation and scalability of the ER4STEM project products, as well as attempting at common frame for the design of educational robotics activity paths.

Generic Curriculum Path Name – a short user-friendly title of the learning path. It should contain keywords, related to the domains targeted by the activities, which allow the reader to recognize a use case that they would want to implement. Provide the title of the activity as it is mediated to relevant stakeholders.

A visual representation of the progression between educational robotics activity plans. It allows for easier communication of ideas and plans to relevant stakeholders.

- A Generic Curriculum Path begins with an entry point, allowing for students of mixed ability and/or no prior knowledge in robotics, STEM or programming. The entry point is an Activity Plan, designed for all children, which could be easily adapted to fit a range of age groups or skills levels.
- The activities need not necessarily be structured based on gradual complexity in terms of subject-related objectives.
- If activities are added or removed from a Generic Curriculum Path, they should be structured as another Generic Curriculum Path.
- Alternative Generic Curriculum Paths (marked on the Generic Curriculum Map with dashed lines) are paths, which allow for an alternative intersection with other Generic Curriculum Paths and allow for an easier switch to other Generic Curriculum Paths.

Brief description of the use case – a summary of the key purpose of the Generic Curriculum Path. This is essential to make a decision about further detailed analysis of the Generic Curriculum Path

Environment: indoors/outdoors

Total duration: The sum of the durations of all Activity Plans, that represents the maximum duration of the generic curriculum path (in hours). Teachers might choose to shorten the overall duration of the curriculum path.

Robotic artifact: i.e. an aggregated report on all applied robotics technologies in the Generic Curriculum Path

Digital artifact: i.e. the programming language applied, visual interface, robot simulation

Within the ER4STEM Activity Plans Template of each activity is given categories and the level of emphasis on concepts from STEAM, Business, Art, Societal Issues and Life Skills is rated (from 0-min to 10-max).

In this section, we represent graphically the max of all values and domains that the Activity Plans comprising the Generic Curriculum Path address. **Example:**

Every ER4STEM Activity Plan is structured by the Generic Curriculum as targeting either a) basics of programming and robotics, b) construction of smart devices, c) solution of real-world problems with pre-set robots or built by students.

In this section, we represent graphically the number of Activity plans within a Generic Curriculum Path under each of these three categories. **Example:**

Social & action: An aggregated report of the social and action skills-related learning outcomes for all the Activity Plans within a Generic Curriculum Path.

E.g. Develop collaborative skills take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice.

Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: An aggregated report on the social and argumentation and fostering of maker culture related learning outcomes for all the Activity Plans within a Generic Curriculum Path.

E.g., practice making conjectures about how the robot will react to external stimuli based on the program given or formulate and define an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.

STEM Concept: An aggregated report on the subject-related desired learning outcomes for all the Activity Plans within a Generic Curriculum Path.

e.g.1 Study the angle and position of all materials (servo motors, circuits, sensors), as well as the construction of the legs in order for the robot - insect to be autonomous and move correctly

With this template, we want to encourage educators from across Europe and even beyond, to contribute to the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum on educational robotics with their own Activity Plans and Generic Curricula paths.

ESI CEE will integrate new Generic Curriculum Paths, if the ER4STEM principles are followed within their creation. This might ultimately lead to the creation of more than one Generic Curriculum Map, if the

use cases underlying the Generic Curriculum Paths' created allow for logical division of Generic Curriculum Paths into two or more Generic Curriculum Maps.

4 GENERIC CURRICULUM: CONTENT

In this report, we present the final version of the Generic Curriculum content as it was in August 2018. It is important to note that D4.3 Final Release of Activity Plans and D2.4 ER4STEM Curriculum are planned to be finalized in parallel during the same month.

4.1 GENERIC CURRICULUM MAP

The Generic Curriculum Map is the contextual visualization of educational robotics learning opportunities, as organized content into a set of use cases and contexts, revolving around desired learning outcomes. It is a part of the context layer of the Generic educational robotics Curriculum under the ER4STEM project.

The inspiration behind the map are the city metro maps, visualizing possible ways to transfer from one point to another (prior knowledge, entry points and desired learning outcomes), the respective metro stations (the ER4STEM Activity Plans) that comprise metro lines (in our case – the Generic Curriculum Paths, more about them in 3.2 of the current deliverable) and stations where lines could be changed.

Our work in this dimension focuses on what the central ideas are around which the activities evolve and how these are expressed in the robotic constructions. Powerful ideas are a central theoretical construct of constructionism and involve the use of knowledge in new ways where learners can establish personal epistemological connections with various domains of knowledge [10]. Furthermore, powerful ideas [11] can be described as domains of knowledge where many diverse topics or subjects co-exist and become explicit.

During the adaptation or the conceptual design of an educational robotics activity, the current contextual background of the ER4STEM might be applied as a reference or as a guideline on choosing suitable activity, based on the experience of the ER4STEM project partners.

The rationale behind the generic educational robotics curriculum map, presented in Figure 4, is multi-layered. On the one hand, it organizes the Activity Plans developed by the project partners in a brief but yet structured way – e.g. by age group, targeted domains, etc., which enables it to serve as a table of contents for the Activity Plans. On the other hand, it will allow pedagogues, teachers and other relevant stakeholders, who are unfamiliar with educational robotics to construct an educational robotics curriculum on a higher level, based on their needs.

With this generic educational robotics frame, we want to assist teachers in adapting a Generic Curriculum Path, consisting of a set of educational robotics activities, that are suitable for their students, based on specific objectives, prior knowledge requirements and the student's interests, strengths and even weaknesses, age and abilities. The idea we want to put forward with this generic curriculum is that of an individual approach to every class or group of students. This resonates with the idea of the project to include all students – not only those who already have experience or are already passionate about robotics. Our aim is to offer educational robotics as a learning tool for every student, regardless of age, ability and prior knowledge.

ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map

TOWARDS A GENERIC CURRICULUM FOR EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS IN STEM: FROM SCIENTIFIC CONCEPTS TO TECHNOLOGIES AND POWERFUL IDEAS

ER4STEM Generic Curricula - Map_FinalDraft_v12_082018

- **BASICS OF PROGRAMMING AND ROBOTICS**
- **CONSTRUCTION OF SMART DEVICES**
- **SOLUTION OF REAL-WORLD PROBLEMS**

Activity Plans by AcrossLimits

- AL 01 Exploring with Dash and Programming with Dash
- AL 02 Engaging with Robots in a Fun Way

Activity Plans by Cardiff University

- CU 01 Basic Introduction to SLurtles
- CU 02 SLurtles Introduction, Orientation and Constructing
- CU 03 Building Our Virtual World

Activity Plans by European Software Institute - Center Eastern Europe

- ES 01 Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop
- ES 02 Visualizing Mathematics with the MathBot
- ES 03 Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills

Activity Plans by Practical Robotics Institute Austria

- PR 01 Design Thinking and Robotics Workshop
- PR 02 Elementary LEGO Mindstorms
- PR 03 Robotics 4 Kids

Activity Plans by Technical University of Vienna

- TU 01 Basic Introduction to Robotics and VPL (v1 & v2)
- TU 02 Robot Elevator

Activity Plans by University of Athens - Educational Technology Lab

- UA 01 An Introduction to Robotics - Exploring Planet Ektonis
- UA 02 Insects' Battle
- UA 03 Park the Robot / The Parking Procedure
- UA 04 Robot Olympics
- UA 05 Robotic Insect
- UA 06 Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine
- UA 07 Building a Robot and Making it Smart

Figure 4 ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

4.2 GENERIC CURRICULUM PATHS AGGREGATION

The Generic Curriculum Paths as a concept are understood as a curriculum property of a suggestive nature. Thus, they present certain relationships between the ER4STEM Activity Plans – the **Activity Plans are connected to each other where a common desired learning outcome is identified, or a common context, such as technology or applied programming languages are taught.** However, educators who might analyze some Activity Plans are bound to find other relationships between Activity Plans, other learning outcomes that might suit their classroom needs, as well as identify other Generic Curriculum Paths that might better fit their context.

The following Aggregation of the Generic Curriculum Paths will assist teachers, researchers and educators in general in identifying concepts, stipulated within the Activity Plans, comprising a Generic Curriculum Path, which correspond directly to their desired learning outcomes, be it social and action related, argumentation and fostering of maker culture related or subject-related. The Generic Curriculum Paths Aggregation serves the meso level of the content layer of the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Framework.

1. Technology and Engineering with LEGO

Technology and Engineering with LEGO																													
<p>Logical layout of the use case: An educator aims to teach technology and engineering with LEGO robots. This could be considered as a typical use case of using robots for education.</p>																													
<p>Suitable for: in-school and for extra-curricular Total duration: 47.5 h Robotic artifact: LEGO Robots; Digital artifact: LEGO Programming</p>																													
<p>0 means no coverage in the Curriculum path; 10 means that at least one Activity Plans fully cover the domain. Source: Activity Plans</p>																													
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>0</th> <th>1</th> <th>2</th> <th>3</th> <th>4</th> <th>5</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Basics of programming and robotics</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Construction of smart devices</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Solution of real-world problems with pre-set robots or built by students</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			0	1	2	3	4	5	Basics of programming and robotics							Construction of smart devices							Solution of real-world problems with pre-set robots or built by students						
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Solution of real-world problems with pre-set robots or built by students																													
<p>0 means no coverage in the Curriculum path; 5 means that at least one Activity Plans fully cover the domain. Source: expert judgment</p>																													

Social & action: Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, analysis and synthesis of solutions. Taking and exchanging roles in a group. Communicate with other groups to find solutions

Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: Class discussion; Students make and test hypotheses in practice about the robot actions based on their own program, make assumptions, test possible solutions, trying to develop their strategy in order to achieve the best solution, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”, collaborate with others “makers”, decision taking, brainstorming, identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions.

STEM Concept: **S:** direction, speed; **T:** code, using sequential programming, loops, selection; sequential programming; **E:** robot, servo motors, circuits, sensors; **M:** angle, curve, square, right angle, multiplication, proportions

2. Science, Technology and Engineering (multiple technologies)

Science, Technology and Engineering (multiple technologies)															
<p>Brief description of the use case: An educator aims to teach concepts of science, technology and engineering while demonstrating various technology platforms such as Arduino, BeeBots, Hedgehog, LEGO Mindstorms and LEGO WeDo as well as a vast plethora of programming languages C++, Python, LEGO Mindstorms Programming, Scratch or SNAP.</p>															
<p>Suitable for: in-school activity Total duration: 77.5 h Robotic artifact: Arduino, Hedgehog, LEGO Mindstorms, LEGO WeDo Digital artifact: Arduino IDE (C++), Python, LEGO Mindstorms Programming, Scratch/SNAP</p>															
<table border="1"> <caption>Curriculum Coverage Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Domain</th> <th>Coverage Score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Science</td> <td>7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Technology</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Engineering</td> <td>8.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mathematics</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Business</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Arts</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>0 means no coverage in the Curriculum path; 10 means that at least one Activity Plans fully cover the domain. Source: Activity Plans</p>		Domain	Coverage Score	Science	7	Technology	8	Engineering	8.5	Mathematics	5	Business	2	Arts	2
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Activity Plan	Coverage Score														
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Solution of real-world problems with pre-set...	2														

Social & action: Creativity, learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas; Develop collaborative skills, fostering of presentation skills, take roles within groups, solve practical problems as a team, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, compare strategies and artefacts.

Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: Communication: While working in teams, students build a robot following generic guidelines. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas how to construct the body of the robot to correctly connect the electronics and to program the robot. Students are made aware by tutors that they would make mistakes and have to identify and rework the corresponding parts in order to build and program the robot. ; Practice making conjectures about how the robot will react based on the program given. ; Students make and test hypotheses in practice about the robot actions based on their own program, make assumptions, test possible solutions, trying to develop their strategy in order to achieve the best solution; Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution.

STEM Concept: **S:** distance, direction, speed, orientation; **T:** code, using sequential programming, loops, selection; **E:** robot, robotics elements, Arduino microcontrollers, motor drivers, ultrasonic sensors, servo motors, circuits, analogue and digital sensor; **M:** angle, curve, square, right angle, multiplication, rectangle, proportions, dimensions, variables, geometry patterns

3. Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM)

Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM)															
<p>Brief description of the use case: An educator aims to cover all STEM domains, Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, while also developing creativity among the students.</p>															
<p>Suitable for: in-school activity Total duration: 56 h Robotic artifact: Arduino, Finch, LEGO WeDo, Thymio; CBiS RobotArm Kit Digital artifact: Aseba, Scratch/SNAP, Blockly</p>															
<table border="1"> <caption>Curriculum Coverage Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Domain</th> <th>Coverage Score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Science</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Technology</td> <td>7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Engineering</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mathematics</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Business</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Arts</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Domain	Coverage Score	Science	5	Technology	7	Engineering	8	Mathematics	5	Business	0	Arts	2
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	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Basics of programming and robotics								
Construction of smart devices								
Solution of real-world problems with pre-set robots or built by students								

0 means no coverage in the Curriculum path; 5 means that at least one Activity Plans fully cover the domain. Source: expert judgment

Social & action: Creativity, learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas; Develop problem solving skills; Exercise effective communication skills; Encourage flexibility and adaptability; Foster collaboration skills; Argumentation; School classes are split up into groups. Each group has its own area of responsibility (design, programming etc.); Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, solve practical problems as a team, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips.

Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: Communication: While working in teams, students build a robot following generic guidelines. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas. Students would make mistakes and have to identify and rework the corresponding parts in order to build and program the robot; Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas; Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; decision-making process within a team; Identifying and solving problems; Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking; Practice making conjectures about how the robot will react based on the program given.

STEM Concept: **S:** direction, distance, speed, orientation; **T:** code, using sequential programming, loops, selection; sequential programming; **E:** robot, servo motors, circuits, sensors robot, robotics elements, Arduino microcontrollers, motor drivers, ultrasonic sensors; horizontal sensors, ground sensors; event-based programming; **M: two and three dimensional coordinate systems, proportion, symmetry,** angles, types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral), types of triangles by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse), circles, radius, diameter, functions (multiplication addition, subtraction and division), positive and negative numbers, whole numbers and decimal numbers, dimensions, variables.

4. "White-Box" Science, Technology and Engineering

"White-Box" Science, Technology and Engineering
<p>Brief description of the use case: An educator aims to teach concepts in science, technology and engineering through "white box" platforms such as: Arduino, Hedgehog, LEGO WeDo with a stronger focus on electronics and widely used industrial programming languages such as C++ and Python</p>
<p>Suitable for: in-school activity Total duration: 42 h Robotic artifact: "All White Box:" Arduino, Hedgehog, LEGO WeDo; Digital artifact: IDE (C++), Python, Scratch</p>

5. Technology, Mathematics and Arts

Robotic artifact: Dash and Dot; Finch (can be replaced by Dash and Dot), SLurtles (virtual robot), CBiS RobotArm Kit
Digital artifact: Drag and Drop, Scratch

0 means no coverage in the Curriculum path; 10 means that at least one Activity Plans fully cover the domain. Source: Activity Plans

0 means no coverage in the Curriculum path; 5 means that at least one Activity Plans fully cover the domain. Source: expert judgment

Social & action: Develop collaborative skills, learn how to take turns and listen to each other, reach a compromise and decision etc.; Allowed students to collaborate and share ideas with each other, and, to learn that decision making processes are enhanced when being teams/groups. Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Develop written communication skills. Communicating with others. Develop written communication skills. Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Working with others in small groups to solve a problem. Presenting incomplete solutions to others. Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; The games require the decision-making process within a team; ☐ Identifying and solving problems; ☐ Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking;

Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: Groups were encouraged to make the robot intelligent and to work at any point in time and not only once. They were encouraged to test before they tell the tutors that their work was ready. Finding multiple solutions to activities, allowing the robot to respond to external stimuli/obstacles. Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning. Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; ☐ The games require the decision-making process within a team; Identifying and solving problems; Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking;

STEM Concept: **T:** loops, If-then, If-else, repeat-until **E:** robot, sensors **M:** two and three dimensional coordinate systems, proportion, symmetry, square, angle (as a turn); probability, random numbers, variables; triangle, properties of shapes, cube, parallelogram, properties of 2D and 3D shapes, symmetry, square and its properties, properties of 2D shapes, triangles, types of triangles and properties, polygons, irregular shapes, 3D shapes, angles, acute and obtuse angles, angles, types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral), types of triangles by width of angles

(acute, right, obtuse), circles, radius, diameter, functions (multiplication addition, subtraction and division), positive and negative numbers, whole numbers and decimal numbers, variables

6. Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

Technology, Engineering and Mathematics															
<p>Brief description of the use case: An educator aims to teach concepts in Technology, Engineering and Mathematics</p>															
<p>Suitable for: in-school activity Total duration: 46.9h Robotic artifact: Finch (can be replaced by LEGO Mindstorms), SLurtles (virtual robot), LEGO Mindstorms Digital artifact: Scratch, LEGO Mindstorms</p>															
<table border="1"> <caption>Coverage in Curriculum path</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Subject</th> <th>Coverage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Science</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Technology</td> <td>9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Engineering</td> <td>7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mathematics</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Business</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Arts</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>0 means no coverage in the Curriculum path; 10 means that at least one Activity Plans fully cover the domain. Source: Activity Plans</p>		Subject	Coverage	Science	5	Technology	9	Engineering	7	Mathematics	5	Business	0	Arts	2
Subject	Coverage														
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Category	Expert Judgment														
Basics of programming and robotics	5														
Construction of smart devices	1														
Solution of real-world problems with pre-set robots or built by...	1														
<p>Social & action: Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Develop written communication skills. Communicating with others. Develop written communication skills. Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Working with others in small groups to solve a problem. Presenting incomplete solutions to others. Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; The games require the decision-making process within a team; Identifying and solving problems; Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking; Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, compare strategies and artefacts; taking and exchanging roles in a group. Communicate with other groups to find solutions</p>															

Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning. Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; The games require the decision-making process within a team; Identifying and solving problems; Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking; Students make and test hypotheses in practice about the robot actions based on their own program, make assumptions, test possible solutions, trying to develop their strategy in order to achieve the best solution. Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.

STEM Concept: T: loops, sequential programming ; E: sensors, ultrasonic sensor, light sensor, motors
M: square, angle (as a turn); probability, random numbers, variables; triangle, properties of shapes, cube, parallelogram, properties of 2D and 3D shapes, symmetry, square and its properties, properties of 2D shapes, triangles, types of triangles and properties, polygons, irregular shapes, 3D shapes, angles, acute and obtuse angles, angles, types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral), types of triangles by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse), circles, radius, diameter, functions (multiplication addition, subtraction and division), positive and negative numbers, whole numbers and decimal numbers, variables

4.3 ER4STEM ACTIVITY PLANS INTEGRATION AND ANALYSIS

The ERW activities may share common elements but they are also very diverse as they address different aspects of Robotics, such as teaching and learning technology with their success depending on how well these aspects are identified and how well they were addressed. This is partly due to the fact that Robotics as a scientific domain could be very specific compared to other learning technologies:

- a) Robotics is inherently multidisciplinary, which in terms of designing a learning activity might mean collaboration and immersion into different subject matters;
- b) Robotics is extensively used in settings of formal and non-formal learning and thus involving different stakeholders;
- c) Robotics’ tangible dimensions cause perturbations – especially in formal educational setting - which are closely related to the introduction of innovations in organizations and schools (i.e. from considering social orchestrations to establishing or not, connections with the curriculum, etc.);
- d) Robotics is a concrete example of the constructionist philosophy for teaching and learning [4]; it is relevant to the newest learning practices such as the “maker” movement, “Do It Yourself” and “Do It with Others” communities etc.

All this being said, a need from dissociation from the specific learning activities emerged, creating a possibility for development of a more Generic Curriculum instrument, i.e. an Activity Plan template, that:

- will be pedagogically grounded on the particular characteristics of robotics as a teaching and learning tool;
- will be adaptable to different learning settings (formal – non-formal);
- will afford generating different examples of learning activities for different types of kits
- will focus on making explicit the implicit aspects of the learning environment and
- will urge designers to think “out of the box” by reflecting on its content.

Furthermore, the concept of a mediating artefact was adopted to describe a generic learning design instrument that is constructed taking into account:

- a) a specific pedagogical theory; and
- b) the particularities of robotics as technologies.

The Activity Plan template is an abstraction of what we have identified as essential and transferrable elements of learning with robotics. Feedback generated from this process was used to update the Activity Plan template so as a) to have a level of abstraction that it make it adaptable to different settings and b) to have a level of detail that demonstrates the influence of a specific pedagogical approach and addresses the particularities of Robotics.

Gueudet and Trouche [12] focusing mainly on resources and documents designed by teachers (e.g. activity or lesson plans), reveal another dimension of design as they describe it as a tool that not only expresses but also shapes the teacher's personal pedagogies, theories, beliefs, knowledge, reflections and practice. The term they used to describe this process is Documentational Genesis. A core element of this approach is instrumental theory [13] according to which the characteristics of the resources teachers select to use, shape their practice on the one hand (instrumentation) and on the other hand, the teachers' knowledge shapes the use of the resources as teachers appropriate them to fit their personal pedagogies (instrumentalisation). Teacher designs, as a result of the above, intertwined, processes according to Pepin, B. Gueudet, G., & Trouche [14], are evolving or living documents - in the sense that they are continuously renewed, changed and adapted.

Design as an expressive medium for teachers and educators, can also function as an instrument for sharing, communicating, negotiating and expanding ideas within interdisciplinary environments. This property of Activity Plan is linked to the concept of boundary objects and boundary crossing [15]. The focus here is on the artefact (in our case Activity Plan) that mediates a co-design process by helping members of different disciplines to gain understanding of each other's perspectives and knowledge. Educational Robotics for STE(A)M is such an interdisciplinary environment, which involves an understanding of related but different domains (i.e. Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, Mathematics) and involves players from industry, academia and organizers of educational activities.

A problem with all these designs, especially when they involve integration of technologies, is that they are driven by a multitude of "personal pedagogies" the restrictions of which result in adapting technologies to existing practices [16]. Conole [9] argues that the gap between the potential of digital technologies to support learning and their implementation in practice can be bridged with a "mediating artefact" to support teacher designs. She continues claiming that such a mediating artefact should be structured according to specific pedagogic approaches and should focus on abstracting essential and transferable properties of learning activities that are not context bound. The Activity Plan template can play the role of the mediating artefact equipping professionals with a structured means to describe, share and shape their practices. This way we can contribute in addressing the problem of fragmentation in the learning activities regarding the use of Educational robotics.

European approaches to STEM education through robotics in one open operational and conceptual framework. It provides a generic design instrument that identifies critical elements of teaching and learning with robotics based in theory and practice and in that contributes to the description of effective learning and teaching with robotics.

The framework developed under WP1 is intended to be applied along and prior to the generic educational robotics curriculum, in order to serve as a baseline for the design or adaptation of educational robotics activities. It furthermore, explained the common ground and the interconnectivity

behind the educational content addressed by the Activity Plans (for detailed information on the content and the Activity Plans, please refer to WP4 Pedagogical Activities, D4.3 Final Release of Activity Plans).

Within the generic curriculum map, presented in Figure 2, and in order to construct the Generic Curriculum Paths, as described above, we used the Activity Plans, which were implemented and validated in year 3 of the ER4STEM project. Within the tables below (Table 2 and Table 3), we give more details on the Activity Plans that were analyzed and used to create the current version of the curriculum map. In Table 2, we provide a legend to translate the Activity Plan codes, implemented within the generic curriculum map. Table 2 is an integrated part of the generic curriculum map within and it serves as part of the map's "legend". Through this table, the relevant stakeholders will be able to identify all Activity Plans included in a current path and further analyze them.

In Table 3, we present an analysis of the Activity Plans for year 3 provided by the project partners. We have used this table in order to analyse and display the relationships between Activity Plans and to structure the activity paths, which we presented above. This table is not part of the generic curriculum or the curriculum map itself, but it is a part of the analysis of the Activity Plans, included within the map. Through it, we could explain the common criteria, through which we grouped certain Activity Plans to create a Generic Curriculum Path.

Table 2 A reference table of Activity Plans codes and Activity Plans names as applied in the current version of the generic educational robotics curriculum

CODE	ACTIVITY PLAN NAME	PARTNER ACRONYM
AL01	Exploring with Dash and Programming with Dash	AcrossLimits
AL02	Engaging with Robots in a Fun Way	AcrossLimits
CU01	Basic Introduction to SLurtles	Cardiff University
CU02	SLurtles Introduction, Orientation and Constructing	Cardiff University
CU03	Building Our Virtual World	Cardiff University
ES01	Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop	ESI CEE
ES02	Visualizing Mathematics with the MathBot	ESI CEE
ES03	Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills	ESI CEE
PR01	Design Thinking and Robotics Workshop	PRIA
PR02	Elementary LEGO Mindstorms	PRIA
PR03	Robotics 4 Kids	PRIA
TW01	Basic Introduction into Robotics and VPL (including the improved V2)	TUWien
TW02	Robot Elevator	TUWien
UA01	Introduction to Robotics - Exploring Planet Ektonis	UoA
UA02	Insects' Battle	UoA
UA03	Park the Robot/The Parking Procedure	UoA
UA04	Robot Olympics	UoA
UA05	Robotic Insect	UoA
UA06	Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine	UoA
UA07	Building a Robot and Making it Smart	UoA

Table 3 ER4STEM Activity Plans Analysis for Representation as Generic Curriculum Elements

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
AL01	No ->		Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals		10		10			Using remote control and Drag and Drop visuals	Develop collaborative skills, learn how to take turns and listen to each other, reach a compromise and decision etc.	Groups were encouraged to make the robot intelligent and to work at any point in time and not only once. They were encouraged to test before they tell the tutors that their work was ready.	1		

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
AL02	Yes	Knowledge of Scratch language for a few of the students which helped with programming of Dash; very few others had attended Lego Mindstorm classes. Other students had no previous knowledge in programming or robotics.	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals		10		10			Drag and drop visuals	Develop collaborative skills, learn how to take turns and listen to each other, reach a compromise and decision etc.	Groups were encouraged to make the robot intelligent and to work at any point in time and not only once. They were encouraged to test before they tell the tutors that their work was ready.	1		

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
CU01	No ->		Slurtles	Scratch for OpenSim		10		3			Programming interface - Scratch for OpenSim; Virtual world – SLurtle World (internal access only); Robot – Slurtles (cuboids)	Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Developed to foster collaboration.	Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning. Developed to foster thinking and problem-solving skills.	1		

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
CU02	No ->		Slurtles	Scratch for OpenSim		10		3			Programming interface - Scratch for OpenSim; Virtual world – SLurtle World (internal access only); Robot – Slurtles (cuboids)	Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Developed to foster collaboration and creativity.	Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning. Developed to foster collaboration, creativity, critical thinking, and teamwork and problem-solving skills.	1		

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
CU03	Yes	Experience in virtual worlds, programming SLurttles to build 2D shapes, communicating with others in the virtual world, documenting their work using screenshots and Sways.	Slurttles	Scratch for OpenSim		10		3		3	Practice and develop programming skills with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim). Develop 3D spatial awareness.	Develop an awareness of how to communicate effectively with others in a virtual world. Developed to foster collaboration and creativity.	Design and create an interactive object within the virtual world. Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Explain ideas to others. Identify and solve problems together. Reflection for learning. Developed to foster collaboration, creativity, teamwork, critical thinking and problem solving.	1		

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
ES01	No ->		Arduino	Scratch	5	10	10				Arduino custom robotics kit.	<p>Creativity: within the workshop students learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas to address real life problems using Tony Buzan mind-mapping techniques.</p> <p>Collaboration: While students in each team are changing their roles during each task, they learn how to work effectively and respectfully with others in order and to build relevantly complex robotics system.</p>	<p>Communication: While working in teams, students build a robot following generic guidelines. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas how to construct the body of the robot to correctly connect the electronics and to program the robot. Students are made aware by tutors that they would make mistakes and have to identify and rework the corresponding parts in order to build and program the robot.</p>		1	

ES02	Yes	Assumed third grade (Bulgarian education system) mathematics knowledge. Basic command of Scratch is a recommendation but not an obligation.	The Finch robot	Scratch		5	10			Programming The Finch robot developed by Birdbrain Technologies with the visual programming software Scratch.	Develop problem solving skills; · Exercise effective communication skills; · Encourage flexibility and adaptability; · Foster collaboration skills; Argumentation	Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. · Encourage curiosity; · Encourage tinkering and experimentation; · The games require the decision-making process within a team; · Identifying and solving problems; · Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot. · Exercise logical thinking;	1		
ES03	No ->		The RobotArm kit by CBiS Education	Scratch		3	4			Programming the RobotArm kit by CBiS Education through the	Develop problem solving skills; Exercise effective	Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas.			1

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
											visual programming software Scratch.	communication skills; Encourage flexibility and adaptability; Foster collaboration skills;	Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; The games require the decision-making process within a team; Identifying and solving problems; Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking;			

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
PR01	Yes	Basic reading skills and understanding of numeric values; Basic knowledge of working with computers is advantageous.	Hedgehog	Python		6	10				Hedgehog Educational Robotics Controller	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, fostering of presentation and argumentation skills. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, teamwork, critical thinking.	Practice explanation and justification of ideas, make assumptions, test possible solutions, and choose the best solution. Designed to foster collaboration, teamwork and critical thinking skills.			1

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
PR02	Yes	Little if any knowledge of the Lego Mindstorms EV3 kit; Reading and writing skills	LEGO Mindstorms	Drag and Drop Visuals		6	10				LEGO EV3 programming environment	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, fostering of presentation and argumentation skills. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, teamwork, critical thinking.	Practice explanation and justification of ideas, make assumptions, test possible solutions, and choose the best solution. Designed to foster collaboration, teamwork and critical thinking skills.	1		

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
PR03	Yes	Little if any knowledge of the Lego Mindstorms EV3 kit; reading and writing skills; basic knowledge of working with computers is advantageous	LEGO EV3	Drag and Drop Visuals		6	10				LEGO EV3 programming environment	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, fostering of presentation and argumentation skills. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, creativity, teamwork and critical thinking.	Practice explanation and justification of ideas, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution. Designed to foster collaboration, teamwork and critical thinking skills.	1		

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
TW01	No ->		Thymio and LEGO	Aseba VPL and Blockly		10	6				Programming with VPL, Blockly; LEGO building stones, use of camera	Divide participants into different size of groups, depending on the amount of kids present. Sometimes we mixed genders, to see how it worked out, sometimes we had them work alone to test their capabilities;	Make them interact with the sensors, the LED's and the shock sensor of the robot and develop an idea about what the robot can and cannot perceive.	1		
TW02			Thymio and LEGO	Aseba Blockly and Textual		10	6				Programming with VPL; LEGO building stones, use of camera	Divide participants into six groups, each of them consists of two people, except for one group of three people to develop their communication and teamwork.	Make them interact with the sensors of the robot and develop an idea about what the robot can and cannot perceive.	1		

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
UA01	Yes	Basic knowledge of programming concepts with Scratch (Sequential instructions, if-then, wait-until)	LEGO WeDo	Scratch	6	7	10	3		2	a) LEGO WeDo 2.0. kit b) Programming in Scratch	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, solve practical problems as a team, and communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips. Using a blog to interact with other groups and group answer to teacher questions.	Practice making conjectures about how the robot will react, based on the program given. Programming a robot is something that a student can do and do it well. Use both Test and try to spiral methodologies. Students must follow guidelines.	1		

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
UA02	Yes	Little if any knowledge of Arduino. Students are experts in electronics and/or have mastery in computer science & programming concepts.	Arduino	Arduino IDE	5	8	8				Programming with Arduino. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, teamwork, problem solving and leadership.	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas, tips and advices. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, teamwork, problem solving, and leadership.	Make assumptions, test possible solutions and choose the best solution. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, creativity, teamwork, critical thinking, problem solving.		1	
UA03	No ->		LEGO NXT	LEGO EV3		10	5	7			Programming with LEGO NXT in LEGO programming environment	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, compare strategies and artefacts	Students make and test hypotheses in practice about the robot actions based on their own program, make assumptions, test possible solutions, trying to develop their strategy in order to achieve the best solution.			1

Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
UA04	Yes	Little knowledge in Robotics; Basic knowledge in programming;	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO EV3	7	9	8	9			Programming LEGO in LEGO programming environment	Develop collaborative skills; communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips.	The aim of the work is to understand the importance of sensors in the control of robotic structures, as well as the natural laws behind human activity.	1		
UA05	Yes	Little knowledge of Arduino and electronic parts (resistances, led). Before this project students were involved in activities in order to get familiar with electronic circuits and Arduino board; Good knowledge of programming concepts (like if-then concepts);	Arduino	Arduino IDE	8	8	8			4	Design with Arduino Uno board, a mini breadboard, some electronic parts (resistances, led, sonar sensor, piezo, servomotor) and programming with open-source Arduino Software (IDE). Skills to be fostered are collaboration, creativity, teamwork, critical thinking and problem solving.	Improve collaborative skills, exchange ideas, and take roles within groups. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, teamwork and leadership.	Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, creativity, teamwork, leadership.		1	

UA06	No ->	LEGO Mindstorms	Logo and LEGO		10	7	10			Programming with Logo and LEGO NXT MINDSTORMS programming environment	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, analysis and synthesis of solutions	Argue about what a camp needs, therefore what solids they need to create and for what reasons. Argue about the spatial arrangement of the camp so that it will be able to support the needs of the people who live there. Practice making conjectures about how the real machine moves in order to cut steel nets which when tiled create container houses. Practice making conjectures about how the robot will move in order to draw nets which when tiled create houses models. Make assumptions, test possible solutions choose the best solution, communicate with other "makers".			1
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Code	Prior knowledge required	Knowledge	Robot	Programming language	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture	Basics of programming and robotics	Construction of smart devices	Solution of real-world problems
UA07	No ->		LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms		10	6	2		2	Programming in LEGO programming environment, assembling LEGO sensors and motors	Taking and exchanging roles in a group. Communicate with other groups to find solutions	Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions choose the best solution, communicate with other "makers".	1		

5 GENERIC CURRICULUM: PROCESS

This final version of the Generic Process aims to serve as reference to teachers, educators, researchers and other relevant stakeholders who would like to apply educational robotics as a tool to maintain student's curiosity in the STEM subjects, but also to provide them with opportunities to develop the so needed 21st century skills.

The scope of the process for the implementation of educational robotics workshops is limited to the adaptation and delivery of the workshops and does not cover educational robotics workshops pedagogical design, which is a subject of WP4 or the educational robotics workshops evaluation, which is a subject of WP6. Although some elements of this process might be adapted for the organization of competitions, it is noteworthy that a separate process for the organization of competitions is available in D3.4 of WP3. So, the process presented below is only concerned with the processes around the implementation of educational robotics workshops.

The Generic Process aims to provide a clear picture to researchers and teachers on the key steps that were planned and executed within the ER4STEM project for the implementation of educational robotics workshops. From a research perspective, the process complements the evaluation data received from the workshops with detailed information on how this data was generated. This section of the report describes the process as it was implemented within the ER4STEM project experience in retrospective and mainly builds on the process for the workshop implementation, as executed during ER4STEM project year 3. Throughout the course of the ER4STEM project, the overall process, its phases, descriptions and criteria were continuously improved and updated based on the experience gained and the feedback received from relevant stakeholders and educational robotics workshops beneficiaries (students, teachers, school representatives and school management). The rest part of this sections includes an essential overview of the process and its phases, which are be further broken down logically.

The Generic Process for the implementation of educational robotics workshops contains four phases, namely Initiation, Preparation, Execution, and Closure that are visually represented within the process scheme as horizontal lines. Those phases follow the basic content structure on a macro level of the ER4STEM project Framework, and namely level two, implementation and level four, improvement (where the process gives evaluation guidelines, crucial for the improvement of the workshop, regardless of research purposes). The "Preparation" and "Delivery" steps are presented in more details as sub-processes.

Overall, each step contains the following properties:

- *Entry criteria*: criteria, which determines when the respective step could be initiated.
- *Inputs*: materials, results from other steps and other items that are needed for the proper execution of the corresponding steps.
- *Outputs*: results produced during the corresponding steps.
- *Exit criteria*: criteria, which determines whether the respective step could be considered completed.

The Generic Process included in this final report incorporates changes and improvements made throughout the ER4STEM implementation period and serves as an updated and final version of the Generic Process, already published in previous deliverables. Although the updates do not change the

process's structure, they reflect on two very important issues 1) the need for closer cooperation with teachers/tutors for the workshops and educational materials' organization and preparation 2) the alignment of the content of educational robotics activities to the curricula of other disciplines, included but not limited to science, technology, engineering and mathematics domains and 3) the need for continuous improvement of the workshops, by sharing experience, data, Activity Plans and other relevant information with stakeholders in order to obtain feedback and contribute to the educational robotics community in Europe and beyond.

Another important factor, which is a subject mainly discussed in WP4 and WP6 of the ER4STEM project, is the importance of providing students with opportunities to develop and exercise 21st century skills. For more information on how to structure educational robotics Activity Plans, targeting scientific domains but also focusing on 21st century skills, read D4.4, as this process is of generic nature and does not go in depth with the processes around the pedagogical design of educational robotics activities.

Other important changes were associated with the related artefacts and methods:

- In Y3 with the release of the full functionalities of the ER4STEM repository on educational robotics, we emphasized on the importance of sharing and continuously improving existing activities.
- Furthermore, with the pedagogical tools developed under WP4 throughout the years, such as Activity Plans, Activity Reports and Activity Blocks, this Generic Process for the implementation of educational robotics activities recommends to all its users to apply these tools to become elaborate about pedagogical design and provide more links to opportunities for engaging students in 21st century skills exploration.
- In Y2, improvements in the evaluation method and tools were introduced. Those improvements are described in further detail in D6.4 Evaluation and Analysis of 2nd Project Year.
- With the finalized Generic Curriculum Map for educational robotics along with the other properties surrounding the Map (see ER4STEM Generic Curriculum), navigation around already existing ER4STEM educational robotics activities became easier and the implementation of educational robotics workshops more detailed in terms of context, content and process. In this Generic Process for the implementation of educational robotics workshops, we aim at encouraging relevant stakeholders to benefit from the tools developed under the ER4STEM project, including the Generic Curriculum.

ERW Implementation Process Description

The ERW Implementation process, presented below starts with an Initiation stage. At this stage, the major objective is to identify, through the aid of the Generic Curriculum Map, desired learning outcomes, that might overlap with those covered by ER4STEM. In addition we aim to assess if the Generic Curriculum Map covers the available technology of the educator, or the programming languages taught already. Defining those aspects will make it easier to identify possible support provided by the ER4STEM Framework on educational robotics in order to make all relevant stakeholders aware and to establish the generic learning objectives on a contextual level. Once the stakeholders are committed to the ERW, we enter into the Preparation stage in which an individual Curriculum Path is tailored from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum and the contents of the activity are documented with the means of an Activity Plan template in alignment to the stated learning objectives. Commitment from all ERW stakeholders is obtained and the ERW is prepared in terms of space, team, materials and evaluation (see Figure 4 Prepare for ERW Delivery Sub-process).

Within the next phase, an ERW is delivered, while the team is performing continuous evaluation (see Figure 6 Deliver ERW Sub-process). The process ends with an analysis and this way, the evaluation results enter the next cycle in order to improve the future educational robotics workshops.

Figure 5 ERW Implementation Process (updated)

PROCESS ELEMENTS

INITIATION PHASE

SELECT GENERIC CURRICULUM PATH (NEW STEP)

Description

An educator or a representative of the Implementation Team conducts an initial analysis of the generic educational robotics curriculum, to identify possible Generic Curriculum Paths or single activities that might be useful to their specific context.

- Analyse the experience already shared within the ER4STEM Repository at repository.er4stem.com;
- Assess and select among activities or Generic Curriculum Paths within the Generic Curriculum Map, which might support the specific learning objectives and context;
- Review the detailed ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Report available for download from the ER4STEM repository (this report);
- Review the Activity Plans comprising the selected Generic Curriculum Paths from the Generic Curriculum and the Generic Curriculum Paths Aggregation;
- Decide which Activity Plans could be adapted to further meet your objectives;

Entry criteria

Desire to implement educational robotics workshops, to support specific learning goals.

Inputs

- Generic Curriculum Map – information on both the context and the content, the process of the generic curriculum on educational robotics, as well as awareness of the support that it might provide to attain specific learning objectives. (Summarized information is available within the ER4STEM Repository at repository.er4stem.com and in detail in the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Report available for download from the ER4STEM repository (this report);
- Activity Plans including key information how to organize the workshop. Summarized information is available within the ER4STEM Repository at repository.er4stem.com. Activity Plans could be downloaded as .pdf files from the ER4STEM Repository on educational robotics;
- References from teachers or workshop leaders, including custom materials, video, “how – to” and others. Summarized information will be available within ER4STEM Repository at repository.er4stem.com.

Outputs

- A list of relevant activities and Generic Curriculum Paths, which might provide support to the design and implementation of educational robotics activities;
- Analysis on how the educational robotics workshops correspond to the curricula related to other disciplines related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics;
- Awareness on the general implementation criteria, target groups, learning objectives;

- Chosen Generic Curriculum Path from the Generic Curriculum Map and its Activity Plans;
- Analysis and assessment of the available infrastructure, which might be of use for the implementation of educational robotics workshop.

Exit criteria

Generic Curriculum Paths and Activity Plans are looked into and one or more of them are selected as a baseline for the design and implementation of educational robotics workshops.

AWARE STAKEHOLDERS

Description

Representative/representatives of the Implementation Team takes actions for raising awareness within the target groups about the benefits of integrating ER in the educational process in alignment to the chosen Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map and its respective Activity Plans. One or several awareness activities could be performed within this step:

- Distribution of awareness materials via electronic channels such as e-mail, social media, broadcasting;
- Consultations with higher level management on how the chosen Generic Curriculum Path from the Generic Curriculum Map and its respective Activity Plans can contribute to the strategic objectives of the organization or school;
- Consultations with teachers on specific subjects related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics, how their disciplines can be supported through educational robotics;
- Close cooperation with teachers and educators, if possible, in order to tailor the educational content presented in the workshop, to the student's needs. This means putting stronger focus on some concepts included already in the Activity Plans or the formulation of an entirely new Activity Plans and educational content;
- Participation in different educational events, such as workshops, conferences, meetings and others;
- Direct meetings with relevant stakeholders;
- Others.

Entry criteria

A Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map and its Activity Plans are selected.

Inputs

- Summary of the selected Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map;
- Information and demonstration materials - video, printed materials, multimedia presentations, robots or robotic kits ready for demonstration, analysed data from previously implemented educational robotics workshops;
- Curricula of the targeted disciplines related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics;
- References from teachers, including material already covered throughout the school year in the official school curricula;
- Representatives from implementation team to be involved in this process are selected and the relevant materials are provided. Target groups are identified, as well as relevant educational events.

Outputs

- Relevant stakeholders, who are interested in organizing the selected ERWs;
- Analysis how the educational robotics workshops correspond to the curricula related to other disciplines related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics;
- General requirements about the implementation of educational robotics workshops communicated to the interested parties.

Exit criteria

Stakeholders are interested in participating in and contributing to the educational robotics workshops.

ARE STAKEHOLDERS INTERESTED?

Gates

- NO
- YES

OBTAIN COMMITMENT FROM STAKEHOLDERS

Description

Representatives of the Implementation Team meet decision makers from the organization that will host/ organize the ERWs. Both parties discuss and agree on important aspects of the ERW delivery such as:

- Learning objectives and expected results related to the targeted discipline and curricula;
- Space and student's info;
- Technical requirements and necessary equipment;
- Content of written consent forms and evaluation procedure.

Entry criteria

The relevant stakeholder is interested to organize/contribute to a Generic Curriculum Path, which is aligned with the general curricula of other disciplines related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics.

Inputs

- Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map ERW Activity Plans;
- Written consent forms for parents, students, teachers and school;
- Information/ demonstration materials and presentations.

Outputs

- Alignment of the requirements of the Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map and/or ERW Activity Plans to the specific objectives and curricula;
- Alignment of the requirements of the Written Consent Forms, if needed;
- Official agreement between implementation organization and hosting organization (if necessary);

- List of participants and necessary information about them and their participation;
- Signed consent forms from parents, students and educational organization.

Exit criteria

Commitment to organize/contribute to the ERWs.

ARE STAKEHOLDERS COMMITTED?**Gates**

YES, but alignment needed

YES

NO

ALIGN GENERIC CURRICULUM PATHS AND ACTIVITY PLANS**Description**

The Implementation Team aligns, if possible and if necessary, the Generic Curriculum Paths and the selected Activity Plans and/or Written Consent Forms to the needs and requirements of the stated objectives, curricula of other disciplines related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics or teachers' requirements. The needs and requirements may include:

- Specific educational objectives. For instance, objectives might need to be changed because students are already advanced in some of the topics covered by ERW or in case that the curricula on other disciplines require additional topics to be included in the workshop in order to meet educational objectives derived from other fields and subjects in science, technology, engineering and mathematics domains.
- Technical constraints derived from the environment. For example, the host organization does not have enough computers available or the computers might be running on a different operation system.
- Organizational requirements. For example, the host organization requires different social orchestration, such as number of students per class, specific criteria for setting up the teams or the available time slots are different from the originally planned time slots in the ERW Activity Plans.

The Implementation Team in cooperation with local teachers/tutors adapts the original Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map, Workshop Activity Plan and/or Written Consent Forms, as needed, in order to satisfy the agreed on requirements provided by the hosting organization. Bi-directional traceability between the aligned Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map, Activity Plan or Written Consent Forms and related activities, materials and artefacts is ensured.

Entry criteria

Changes to the Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map, Activity Plan or Written Consent Form are requested and agreed upon.

Inputs

- Original Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map;
- Original ERW Activity Plan;
- Original Written Consent Forms;
- Information Materials;
- Alignment of requirements to the Generic Curriculum Map and ERW Activity Plan;
- Alignment of requirements to the Written Consent Forms.

Outputs

- Aligned Activity Plan, including clear instruction how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts;
- Aligned written consent forms;
- Aligned information materials.

Exit criteria

Commitment to the Aligned Activity Plan and/or Written Consent Forms is obtained by all relevant stakeholders

OBTAIN COMMITMENT FROM ERW PARTICIPANTS

Description

The Implementation Team distributes information brochures and Written Consent Forms among the participants (students and their families), answers any questions, and comments that come from the participants or their parents.

Local teachers/tutors or scientists are committed to contribute to the ERWs and to learn how to implement them.

Majority of the participants in the ERW sign written consent forms and are familiar with the study and the purpose of data collection and have understanding on how their identity and their data will be protected.

Entry criteria

Obtained commitment to the Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map and the Activity Plans from the ERW organizers/ host.

Inputs

- List of participants;
- Written Consent Forms Templates - for organizer/ host, for the participants and their parents;
- Information materials related to the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum, workshops and the project and the study (if applicable).

Outputs

- Signed Written Consent Forms - by hosting organization, by parents and students;
- Updated list of participants with marked preferences for video or audio recording, agreement to participate in EC open data initiative, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW process and any other information, relevant to the ERW implementation;

Exit criteria

All participants and relevant stakeholders provided signed written consent forms. Updated list of participants is developed.

PREPARE FOR ERW DELIVERY

[Go to details of the sub-process](#)

Description

The Implementation Team prepares the workshop delivery

Entry Criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders is obtained and the Activity Plans is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Aligned Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map and Activity Plan, including clear instructions how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts;
- Updated list of participants with marked preferences for video or audio recording, agreement to participate in EC open data initiative, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW process and any other information, relevant to the ERW implementation;
- Evaluation templates;
- Evaluation method.

Outputs

- Materials and artefacts prepared;
- Space and ICT environment ensured;
- Implementation team trained;
- Evaluation materials printed.

Exit Criteria

Outputs are finalized and ready.

EXECUTION PHASE

DELIVER ERWS

[Go to details of the sub-process](#)

Description

The Implementation team, ideally in cooperation with other teachers/tutors or scientists executes the selected ERWs in the Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map following the specific Activity Plans and observation/ assessment method, taking into account a target group on which the observation will focus.

Entry Criteria

Workshop prepared

Inputs

- Activity Plans;
- Materials and artefacts;
- Space and ICT environment;
- Implementation team (tutors) trained;
- Observation/ Assessment methods and tools;
- Tools, equipment and spare parts.

Outputs

- Educational results;
- Collected and processed artefacts and observation/ assessment forms;
- Reflections on ERW and improvement suggestions from implementation team and contributing teachers/tutors or scientists.

Exit Criteria

ERW finalized

CLOSURE PHASE

EVALUATE RESULTS

Description

The implementation team or external expert evaluates achieved educational results according to the educational objectives in the Activity Plans and observation/ assessment methodology. Members of the Implementation Team document good practices and issues that were observed and any ideas for improvements that were generated by the relevant stakeholders. Information includes:

- Source (who identified the issue);
- Observation (description of the issue);
- Cause (what caused the issue, if it can be readily identified);
- Suggested improvement (how to solve the problem);

Entry criteria

Delivered educational robotics workshop.

Inputs

- Evaluation method;
- Collected and filed in evaluation documents and educational artefacts;
- Tutor reflections and observations in raw format;
- Improvement suggestions.

Outputs

- Evaluation forms and sheets are filled in by participants and are collected, organized, anonymized and scanned to be further stored in the workshop data base;
- Signed written consent forms are processed and organized into folders;
- Other relevant artefacts of learning, such as code, mind maps, midpoint reflections, etc., are collected;
- Tutor documents, such as tutor observations and tutor reflections are completed;
- Video or audio interviews with preferably the target group from the study, are conducted, transcribed and encrypted;
- Sensitive data, such as participant key, name labels, certificates, photos, videos, etc., is encrypted and stored on an external hard drive;
- Suggestions for improvement and reflections on the workshop are taken into consideration and filed;

Exit criteria

Evaluated results.

PROVIDE FEEDBACK

Description

The workshop organizers and tutors provide structured feedback to all relevant stakeholders about the results achieved by the workshops and the Generic Curriculum Path from the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map as a whole. Different communication channels are used e.g. social media, newspapers, press releases, etc.

Entry criteria

Evaluation of the educational robotics workshops is completed.

Inputs

- Generic Curriculum Path;
- Activity Plans;
- Evaluation results.

Outputs

- Publications about the Generic Curriculum Path and ERWs in different media;
- Relevant stakeholders are made aware about the results achieved by the ERWs.

Exit criteria

Relevant stakeholders are made aware for the results achieved by the ERWs.

CONTRIBUTE TO THE ER4STEM REPOSITORY

Description

The ERWs organizers contribute to the ER4STEM repository with their aligned or new Activity Plans and the materials they used to conduct the ERWs in their specific context, along with their desired learning objectives. They share results, experience, non-sensitive evaluation data, observations and other. ER4STEM repository specialists, responsible for the content moderation of the ER4STEM repository review and publish the new information.

Entry criteria

ERWs are evaluated.

Inputs

- Aligned or new Activity Plans and materials;
- Evaluation results;
- Case studies, articles and other materials that describe the experience related to the organization of the workshops.

Outputs

New records in the ER4STEM Repository on educational robotics.

Exit criteria

New records are published in the ER4STEM Repository on educational robotics.

Prepare for ERW Delivery Sub-process

Figure 6 Prepare for ERW delivery sub-process

PROCESS ELEMENTS

SET UP SPACE AND ENVIRONMENT

Description

The Implementation team checks the hall/s where the ERW will take place and ensures that the facilities and equipment correspond to the requirements of the activity, as defined in the respective Activity Plans. When applicable, the Implementation team installs necessary software on the computers that will be used by the students and tests it to make sure that the software is properly set up.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders is obtained and the Activity Plans is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plan including clear instructions how to further involve local teachers/tutors or scientists and how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts.

Outputs

- Space and ICT environment.
- Access to an appropriate workshop hall guaranteed.
- Workshop desks, power supplies and other special tools/equipment ensured.
- ICT equipment ensured and set up as needed.

Exit criteria

Space and ICT requirements fulfilled.

TRAIN THE IMPLEMENTATION TEAM

Description

All members of the implementation team, local teachers/tutors and participating scientists are trained how to facilitate the ERW. If necessary, the team can decide to simulate the workshop and all activities in it. Any specifics of the particular workshop are discussed and actions are planned.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders obtained and the Activity Plans is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plan and/or Curriculum Path, including clear instructions how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts.
- Updated list of participants with written for video recording, agreement to participate in open data pilot, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW and any other information relevant to the ERW implementation.
- Evaluation templates.

- Evaluation method and protocol.

Outputs

- Implementation team, local teachers/tutors and participating scientists trained on:
 - Scenario.
 - Space and students' information.
 - Social orchestration.
 - Student productions and artefacts of learning.
 - Sequence and description of activities.
 - Evaluation procedures, interviews, reflections, observations and sensitive data.

Exit criteria

Implementation team is capable to execute the workshop

SET UP MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

Description

The implementation team prepare the materials and artefacts for the ERW taking into account any specific requirements for the particular workshop. The activities can include:

- Disassembly/assembly of components of the robotic kits.
- Testing each kit/robot to ensure that it functions properly.
- Modification of students and teachers' guides.
- Others.

Integrity (e.g. right versions) of the materials and artefacts ensured.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders obtained and the Activity Plans is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plans including clear instructions how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts.

Outputs

- Materials and artefacts prepared:
 - Digital artefacts.
 - Robotic artefacts.
 - Student's workbook and manual.
 - Teacher's instruction book and manual.

Exit criteria

Materials and artefacts are ready.

PREPARE EVALUATION

Description

The implementation team prints the evaluation forms and ensures equipment for conducting the evaluation during the ERW delivery.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders obtained and the Activity Plan is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Evaluation templates.
- Evaluation method and protocol; Updated list of participants with marked preferences for video recording, agreement to participate in open data pilot, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW and any other information relevant to the ERW implementation.

Outputs

- Evaluation materials printed and/or digitally prepared:
 - Pre-questionnaire form.
 - Post-questionnaire form.
 - Observation notes template.
 - Reflection sheet form.
 - Activity Plan Template.
 - Post-Activity Report Template.
- Focus group for observation and interviews identified.
- Evaluation equipment ready:
 - Camera.
 - Audio/ video recorder.

Exit criteria

Evaluation prepared.

Deliver ERW Sub-process

Figure 7 Deliver ERW sub-process

PROCESS ELEMENTS

INTRODUCE STUDENT TO THE ERW CONTEXT

Description

The researcher introduces the implementation team, explain the ERW objectives, describe the ERW agenda and provides safety instructions. Explain that video/audio recording equipment will be/is set up in the room and why.

Entry criteria

ERW has started

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plans;
- If conducted in a school, informed consent given by the school to carry out the research.
- Informed consent to collect and store data given by parents.
- Informed consent to collect and store data given by students.
- Informed consent to collect and store data given by tutors.
- Signed consent forms stored safely.
- Each student has randomly allocated a student number.

Outputs

- Tutors introduce themselves, the project, the workshop and the study - students are aware of the workshop context and about the study, they will take part in.
- Students are introduced to the evaluation methods, which will be applied during the workshops.
- Students understand that they do not have to consent to take part in the evaluation and that this will not result in any negative consequence for them.
- Students know that they can withdraw from the study at any time, without giving any explanation and this will not result in any negative consequence for them
- Students receive and understand safety instructions for participating in the ERW.

Exit criteria

Introduction done

PRE-QUESTIONNAIRE

Description

The implementation team asks students to fill in the pre-questionnaire form.

- Pre-questionnaire (online or paper copy) collects background information on students and requires their student number.

Entry criteria

Introduction done and students are aware about the ERW objectives.

Inputs

- Pre-questionnaire evaluation form.
- Drawing or writing tools.
- Participant numbers stickers or other way to mark participants' work.

Outputs

- Filled in pre-questionnaire sheets.

Exit criteria

Implementation team collected students' sheets pre-questionnaire

LEAD THE WORKSHOPS SESSIONS

Description

Following the Activity Plan, the implementation team informs students about robotic behaviours, the role of creator-programmer in giving desired functionalities and characteristics to a robotic device. Students are introduced to available parts, sensors, motors. Students create/ assemble robot devices from available parts or consider functionalities/ characteristics of pre-assembled available robotic devices. Students experiment with different values and settings and observe the results during the workshop. Students create programs for controlling the robotic devices. If robotic devices are pre-assembled, the students focus on programming and debugging their own programs. Implementation team leads the students in researching connections with other scientific domains - mathematics, engineering, biology, chemistry etc.

Entry criteria

Collected filled in pre-questionnaire sheets

Inputs

- Activity plan.
- Scenarios.
- Tested and assembled/ disassembled robotic kits.
- Installed programs and applications on student computers.
- Provided guides and instructions.

Outputs

- Pictures and videos (if applicable) of the workshop, the artefacts of learning, etc.
- Assembled robot devices.
- Collect the code that each team produced.
- Observation.
- Mid-point reflections conducted in a format suitable to the case.
- Other artefacts - research description, project design description, problem description etc.

Exit criteria

Collected artefacts of students' work

CONTINUOUS OBSERVATION

Description

The implementation team follows assessment method and tools together with blank sheets of questionnaires and interview questions. The observation is implemented during the whole duration of the workshop. The observation can include one or more of the following elements:

- Interview with focus group(s) (implemented by implementation team).
- Peer assessment.
- Artefacts of learning (code, robots, plans, reflection, etc.).
- Observation notes (filled by the implementation team).
- Reflection sheet (filled by each member of implementation team).

Entry criteria

Designed and developed assessment method and tools.

Inputs

- Developed assessment method.
- Printed supporting documents for tutors (observation forms, interview questions, evaluation protocol, etc.).
- Signed written consent forms - by the host/ organizer of the workshop, parents, students;
- Awareness of the participants in the assessment/ observation, its goals, the evaluation protocol, data and identity protection policies.
- Implementation team is trained how to perform the observation-related activities.

Outputs

- Target group is observed and interesting moments, phrases, reactions are recorded; if audio or video equipment is used for recording, the equipment is also monitored, and observations are timestamped according to the recording.
- Tutor documents, such as tutor observations and tutor reflections are completed and stored in the workshop database.
- Observation is accompanied by evaluation forms and other evaluation-related documents and activities.
- If permitted, audio or video recordings are made.
- Conducted short "interviews" with groups, ask questions and if possible, record them to support the evaluation. Each team could write instead a short team reflection on what they have done so far in the format of a blog post. The team's response is discussed within the team (not a sub-set of the team) and is as honest as possible.

Exit criteria

Collected and filed all observation sheets and tools

CONCLUDE THE WORKSHOP

Description

The implementation team gives students feedback about the workshop, gives last minute advice, internet connections for more information and provides important conclusions. The implementation team collects all observation/ assessment sheets and announces the end of the workshop.

Entry criteria

Collected workshop artefacts and observation sheets.

Inputs

- Developed assessment method.
- Printed assessment tools and supporting documents for tutors (evaluation forms, interview questions, evaluation protocol sheets).
- Signed written consent forms - by the host/ organizer of the workshop, parents, students.
- Awareness of the participants in the assessment/ observation, its goals, the evaluation protocol, data and identity protection policies.
- Implementation team is trained how to perform the evaluation-related activities;
- Microphone and/or camera.
- Post-Questionnaire sheets printed out.

Outputs

- Evaluation forms and sheets are filled in by participants and are collected by tutors.
- Other relevant artefacts of learning, such as code, mind maps, midpoint reflections, etc., are collected.
- Tutor documents, such as tutor observations and tutor reflections are completed.
- Video or audio interviews with preferably the target group with minimum 2 students from the study are performed.

Exit criteria

Artefacts and observation sheets.

PERFORM FINAL EVALUATION

Description

The implementation team processes the collected and filed artefacts and observation sheets according to the evaluation protocol. According to the tutor experience and data (last if applicable), the implementation team suggests improvement actions. The Implementation team performs evaluation.

Entry criteria

Artefacts and evaluation sheets

Inputs

- Developed evaluation method.
- Printed assessment tools and supporting documents for tutors (evaluation forms, interview questions, evaluation protocol sheets).
- Signed written consent forms - by the host/ organizer of the workshop, parents, students.

- Awareness of the participants in the assessment/ observation, its goals, the evaluation protocol, data and identity protection policies.
- Implementation team is trained how to perform the evaluation-related activities;
- Camera and/or microphone.

Outputs

- Observations - video and audio recordings are used to finalise own observation notes.
- Sample materials that represent good practices
- Modified Activity Plans
- Others

Exit criteria

Processed data.

PERFORM FINAL EVALUATION

Description

The implementation team share its experience with other educators.

Entry criteria

Evaluation completed

Inputs

- Evaluation materials
- Registration in the ER4STEM Repository

Outputs

- Lessons learned
- Modified/improve Activity Plans
- New elements or whole ERW.

Exit criteria

Data uploaded in the ER4STEM repository.

6 ER4STEM WORKSHOPS REPORT

The final aggregated data shows that since the start of the ER4STEM project, for the period February 2016 – July 2018 in which WP2 was in implementation, a total of 190 educational robotics workshops with 4459 students or 110% of the 4050⁸ planned students for the whole project were completed.

The number of workshops and workshop participants per project year are shown in the table below.

Table 4 Educational workshops number and student numbers by project year

Project Year	Period of ERWs execution		Number of ERWs per period	Number of students per period	More details reported in:
	from	until			
Year 1 (Y1)	1-Feb-16	31-Jul-16	48	1213	D2.1 Workshop Report 1st Year
Year 2 (Y2)	1-Sep-16	31-Jul-17	70	1570	D2.2 Workshop Report 2nd Year
Year 3 (Y3)	1-Sep-17	31-Jul-18	72	1676	D2.3 Workshop Report 3rd Year
Total Y1, Y2 and Y3	1-Feb-16	31-Jul-18	190	4459	D2.4 ER4STEM curriculum (summary for the 3 years)

Detailed information about the workshops is presented in [Appendix 1 Quantitative data from the ERWs based on the Workshop Information Forms](#).

The workshops were well distributed in the whole project period with a good balance between female and male participant each year, which facilitated learning and improvement of the ERW content and process in each iteration.

The timeline of the ERWs implementation is illustrated in [Figure 8](#) and [Figure 9](#).

⁸ While in the proposal we targeted “more than 4000 students can be reached by the workshops”, the operational plan was to achieve at least 4050 participants in the workshops.

Figure 8 Number of male and female students and number of workshops per month

Figure 9 Cumulative number of male and female students and number of workshops per month

A visual representation of the distribution of educational robotics workshops and the respective number of students per project partner can be seen in Figure 10. This distribution corresponds to the country in which the respective workshops were implemented. PRIA and TUWien implemented 66 workshops with 1515 students in Austria and Italy (1 educational robotics workshop in Italy), ESI CEE implemented 42 workshops with 1143 students in Bulgaria, UoA implemented 26 workshops with 482 participants in Greece, AcrossLimits implemented 36 workshops with 821 participants in Malta and Cardiff University implemented 20 educational robotics workshops with 498 students in UK.

Figure 10 Number of male and female students and number of ERW per project partner

The ERWs were highly appreciated by the students. On average, the workshops were rated by the students with 3.5 to 5 stars out of 5 possible (Figure).

Figure 8 Average number of stars given by ERWs participants per project partner

The participants in the workshops were well balanced in terms of gender (Figure 11). Female participants were 48% of the total number of students and male participants were 52% of the total number of students. With a few exceptions, there were no significant deviations between the shares of female and male students based on variables such as implementing partner, robotics kit and programming languages, which yet makes the research rather balanced in terms of gender in the majority of its aspects.

Figure 11 Number of male and female participants

A total number of participants per workshop ranging between 20 and 29 students was applicable for 126 ERWs (66% of the total number of ERWs), which could be assumed to correspond to the average number of students within a regular classroom in general education schools in Europe, according to statistics by OECD ⁹(Figure 12).

⁹ https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=EDU_CLASS#

Figure 12 Distribution of number of ERWs by number of participants per ERW

Regarding technologies, most of the students from the third year of the project participated in ERW based on Arduino robotics kits (19 %), followed by students that participated in workshops based on the Dash a Dot robotics kits (18%), LEGO Mindstorms robotics kits (13%), Thymio II (12 %) and Slurtle (11%). The remaining participants used Finch (7%) and Hedgehog (6%) while less than 5% used other technologies. (Figure 13). It is worth mentioning that the two technologies developed under WP5 namely, Slurtle and Hedgehog had a significant share within the participants in Y2 and Y3. With the exception of the ERWs based on BotBall, where students were largely boys, the ERWs were generally well balanced in terms of gender.

Robotic Arm Kit - CBiS Education robotic kit was introduced for the first time during the third year of the project and it proved to be promising in applying educational robotics as a medium to teach other disciplines such as mathematics and ecology.

Figure 13 Number of male and female students and number of ERW per robotics kit

The visual programming languages in which participated more than one third of the total number of participants were used with Arduino, Slurtle, Finch, Robotic Arm Kit - CBiS Education and LEGO WeDo robotics kits. Drag and Drop Visuals was used with Dash and Dot in workshops with participation of 18% of the participants. Lego Mindstorms was used by 13% of the participants. It is worth mentioning that the visual programming languages, which are suitable for students without previous programming experience, were complemented by “industrial; programming languages such as Python and C/C++/Arduino. The latest languages, used by 14% of the participants, are directly applicable in industrial environment.

Figure 14 Number of male and female students and number of ERW per programming language

7 CONCLUSION / OUTLOOK

During the implementation phase of WP2 of the ER4STEM project the partners were able to successfully design, implement and evaluate 190 educational robotics workshops with 4459 participants in six countries, while continuously applying key improvements, such as:

- Modifying the Generic Curriculum Process for the implementation of educational robotics workshops in order to take into account all newly developed project tools and pedagogical instruments. The Generic Curriculum Process was further modified to align to the STEM subjects-related curricula and to involve local teachers and educators.
- One new educational robotics technology was introduced within three workshops carried out within the third project year.
- Use of new and revised Activity Plans and Activity Blocks to facilitate the design and implementation of a workshop.
- Introduction of improved evaluation methods and tools.
- Focus on 21st century skills and on the ER4STEM values.

The ER4STEM workshop data along with the Generic Curriculum evolution throughout the entire project lifecycle are documented in D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3, and were finalized, summarised and improved as visualization and description in D2.4 ER4STEM Curriculum (this deliverable). In this deliverable, we managed to further refine data and to correct some minor technical errors from previous deliverables.

In the last year of the project, we managed to adapt the educational robotics workshops implementation process in order to change its focus from implementation by project partners to initiation and implementation by educators, teachers and researchers.

Moreover, we systemized the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum on educational robotics on meso and macro level in order to facilitate and foster the use of the ER4STEM expertise by the target audience. The curriculum is well linked to the ER4STEM Framework and is being integrated within the ER4STEM Repository.

We expect that the Generic Curriculum will be applied by the teachers, educators and researchers in Europe as a tool for designing and managing educational robotics activities within their classrooms. We have already seen such trend in two Bulgarian schools.

One of them, 125 High School “Boyan Popov”, has already adapted some parts of the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum that were used to initiate and sustain a new innovative discipline in the school “Hypothesis, experiment and result”. In that curriculum, educational robotics is used as a main tool to facilitate teaching of mathematical and problem solving concepts. Another school, 2 "Daskal Dimitri" Primary School in Kyustendil, started an adaptation of the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum in their formal education process. More over the school is interested to further use the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum in order to establish an educational robotics club for students aged between 10-15 years old.

During the curriculum, development we were glad to share our experience and to learn from the feedback provided by more than 50 teachers in 4 teacher-training workshops (one in Moldova, two in Kyustendil and one during the teacher workshop at ECER 2017) and by different events including conferences, invited talks, webinars and several workshops organized in cooperation with Scientix.

These and many further events, in which the ER4STEM project partners took place, provided a valuable chance for us to connect with teachers, listen to stories about STEM integration within regular classrooms, and had the chance to assess the usability and clarity of the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum and its products. All these events are listed in D8.3 Educational Robotics Non-Scientific Dissemination.

Four Generic Curriculum-related scientific publications facilitated discussions with relevant stakeholders at three educational robotics or constructionism/pedagogical theory conferences. Writing, conversing and peer reviewing those papers helped us clarify the concepts and discuss them with the researchers' community. Namely, those publications are:

1. Yiannoutsou, N., Nikitopoulou, S., Kynigos, C., Gueorguiev, I., & Angel-Fernandez, J. (2016). Activity Plan Template: A Mediating Tool for Supporting Learning Design with Robotics. *Robotics in Education Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, 3-13. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-42975-5_1
2. Gueorguiev, I., Todorova, C., Varbanov, P., Sharkov, P., Sharkov, G., Girvan, C., Yiannoutsou, N., Grizioti, M. (2018) Educational Robotics for Communication, Collaboration and Digital Fluency. In: Lepuschitz W., Merdan M., Koppensteiner G., Balogh R., Obdržálek D. (eds) *Robotics in Education. RiE 2017. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol. 630. Springer, Cham
3. Christina Todorova, Carina Girvan, Nikoleta Yiannoutsou, Marianthi Grizioti, Ivaylo Gueorguiev, Pavel Varbanov and George Sharkov (2018) Visualizing mathematics with the MathBot: a constructionist activity to explore mathematical concepts through robotics. *Constructionism 2018. Vilnius, Lithuania, August 21-25, 2018.*
4. Gueorguiev, I., Todorova, C., Yiannoutsou, N., Gkreka, C., Girvan, C., Varbanov, P., Sharkov, G., Duca, A., Vittori, L. and Fernandez, J. (2018) Towards a Generic Curriculum for Educational Robotics in STEM: From Scientific Concepts to Technologies and Powerful Ideas. *Constructionism 2018. Vilnius, Lithuania, August 21-25, 2018.*

Through the design, creation and dissemination of this Generic Curriculum on educational robotics, as well as through the valuable contacts with educators, researchers and teachers throughout the years, we know that we contributed to the European education scene.

This gives us confidence to say that the products, created by us as a project consortium within WP2, could and will be further used to support STEM education through robotics, for all children to keep them curious and motivated to learn science, technology, engineering and mathematics.

8 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

AcrossLimits, AL	AcrossLimits, Malta
CU	Cardiff University, UK
Desired learning outcomes	Desired learning outcomes, as understood by the ER4STEM generic curriculum implementation team, lay out what an educator is aiming to convey to students through the educational robotics activity. The term is used in reference to what a student has been able to practice and could be able to transfer to other domains or spheres of life,

during and after the end of an educational robotics session, activity or curriculum path, as planned by the educator.

EC	European Commission
ER	Educational Robotics
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
ERW(s)	Educational Robotics Workshop(s)
ESI CEE	European Software Institute - Center Eastern Europe, Bulgaria
Generic Curriculum	In ER4STEM, we assume the definition of a curriculum being everything that goes in the learners' live such as planned and not planned interaction of pupils with educational objectives, instructional content, materials and resources used and materials and resources not used the sequence of courses, objective, standards and interpersonal relationships (Adams and Adams, 2003).

The Generic Curriculum in ER4STEM is a mediating artifact between the ER4STEM Framework (WP1) and the implementation of ERWs (WP2), integrating products developed in WP4, in alignment with the evaluation results from the workshops (WP6). The **ER4STEM Generic Curriculum** on educational robotics is a structured **methodology** and a **tool** to navigate through **educational robotics activities** (as both educational approach and content), developed and applied by all partners. The

Generic Curriculum Architecture	The ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Architecture represents the structure of all elements comprising the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum on educational robotics. The ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Architecture organizes the Generic Curriculum elements in three levels - macro, meso and micro levels, all of which are further broken down into context, content and process levels.
Generic Curriculum Map	The curriculum map is the contextual visualization of educational robotics learning opportunities, as organized content into a set of use cases and contexts, revolving around desired learning outcomes. It is a part of the context layer of the generic educational robotics curriculum under the ER4STEM project.
Generic Curriculum Path	A tool introduced under the ER4STEM project to address desired learning outcomes through a set of use cases. A Generic Curriculum Path consists of a set of educational robotics workshops or single activities within the workshops activity plans, which are suitable for a given context, students, specific objectives and prior knowledge. A

Generic Curriculum Path is designed to be further modified by the educator to fit their specific learning context.

Generic Curriculum Path Template	As is the Activity Plan Template, the Generic Curriculum Path Template is a design tool of a generic nature. The Generic Curriculum Path Template facilitates different stakeholders to design Generic Curriculum Paths for different robotics toolkits, containing various educational robotics Activity Plans and addressing various STEM domains. This template provides a simple structure serving as the backbone for the formulation of the use cases, or the logic, behind a Generic Curriculum Paths and is the common element between a set of Activity Plans.
Generic Curriculum Paths Aggregation	A table, providing an overview of the core values of every each one of the 6 currently identified Generic Curriculum Paths. It aggregates the 21st century skills and targeted values, as well as the core subject-objectives of the Activity Plans, comprising a Generic Curriculum Path. It further gives an overview of the technologies, programming languages, total duration and targeted STEM domains to help an educator assess the applicability of a Generic Curriculum Path to their unique use case.
Generic Process	The Generic Process aims to provide a clear picture to researchers and teachers on the key steps that were planned and executed within the ER4STEM project for the implementation of educational robotics workshops. The final version of the Generic Process presented within the current deliverable, serves as reference to teachers, educators, researchers and other relevant stakeholders who would like to apply educational robotics as a tool to maintain student's curiosity in the STEM subjects, but also to provide them with opportunities to develop the so needed 21st century skills.
Implementation Team	All members of the team that implements the workshop including but not limited to facilitators, teachers, researchers, evaluators and others.
Local teacher/tutor or scientists	Teacher/tutor or scientists from hosting organizations, school or club.
PRIA	Practical Robotics Institute Austria, Austria
REA	Research Executive Agency
Relevant Stakeholder	A stakeholder that is involvement in specific ERWs activities.
STE(A)M	Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Mathematics
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
TUWien	Vienna University of Technology, Austria

9 CORRECTIONS

In order to prepare the analysis of the Generic Curriculum we had to input and process data for 4459 participants each of them consisting of more than 150 data records. In addition, we collected quantitative data for the 190 workshops.

Although we established and maintained solid quality controls, at the final stage of preparation of our final deliverable, we noticed some errors in the data that was published within the previous deliverables. The aim of this section is to serve as an erratum or a corrigendum note for the other deliverables.

Document, page, paragraph	D2.2 Workshop Report 2 nd Year, page 40, paragraph 1
Written:	“Within the period from October 2016 until July 2017, project partners organized 60 ERWs with 1570 participants”
Should read:	“Within the period from October 2016 until July 2017, project partners organized 70 ERWs with 1570 participants”

Document, page, paragraph	D2.3 Workshop Report 3 rd Year, page 53, paragraph 1
Written:	“Total of 190 educational robotics workshops with 4334 students or 107% of the planned students for the whole project were completed.”
Should read:	“Total of 190 educational robotics workshops with 4459 students or 110% of the planned students for the whole project were completed.”

Document, page, paragraph	D2.3 Workshop Report 3 rd Year, page 68, Column “Age of the students from”, row 56
Written:	“2”
Should read:	“14”

Document, page, paragraph	D2.3 Workshop Report 3 rd Year, page 68, Column “Total number of groups”, row 55 and row 59 and row 60
Written:	“-1”
Should read:	“0”

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APPENDIX 1 QUANTITATIVE DATA FROM THE ERWS BASED ON THE WORKSHOP INFORMATION FORMS

ERW No	Code	Partner name	Dates from	Dates to	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other	Age of students	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male	Number of female	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
Y1-01	AL-1-01	AcrossLimits	5/10/2016	5/12/2016	2	4	0	10	10	24	10	14	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y1-02	AL-1-02	AcrossLimits	5/11/2016	5/13/2016	2	4	0	10	10	27	11	16	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y1-03	AL-1-03	AcrossLimits	5/18/2016	5/19/2016	2	4	0	10	10	20	11	9	2	2	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y1-04	AL-1-04	AcrossLimits	5/26/2016	5/30/2016	2	4	0	10	10	24	10	14	2	2	12	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y1-05	AL-1-05	AcrossLimits	6/13/2016	6/20/2016	2	4	0	10	10	26	17	9	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y1-06	AL-1-06	AcrossLimits	6/21/2016	6/23/2016	2	4	0	8	9	24	16	8	2	2	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y1-07	PRW2-125-3a	ESICEE	2/16/2016	2/23/2016	2	2	2	9	10	28	17	11	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-08	PRW2-137-4a	ESICEE	2/25/2016	2/25/2016	1	2	2	10	10	24	12	12	3	4	6	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-09	PRW2-137-7a	ESICEE	2/29/2016	2/29/2016	1	2	2	12	14	29	12	17	4	5	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-10	PRW2-125-3b	ESICEE	3/1/2016	3/8/2016	2	2	2	9	10	27	12	15	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-11	PRW2-40-2a	ESICEE	3/2/2016	3/9/2016	2	2	2	8	9	32	22	10	3	5	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-12	PRW2-VFU	ESICEE	3/12/2016	3/13/2016	2	3	1	8	14	17	9	8	4	6	5	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-13	PRW2-125-3g	ESICEE	3/15/2016	3/22/2016	2	2	2	9	10	27	16	11	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch

ERW No	Code	Partner name	Dates from	Dates to	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other	Age of students	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male	Number of female	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
Y1-14	PRW2-40-2b	ESICEE	3/16/2016	3/23/2016	2	2	2	8	9	29	20	9	3	5	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-15	PRW2-125-3c	ESICEE	3/18/2016	3/25/2016	2	2	2	9	10	29	14	15	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-16	PRW2-23-4b	ESICEE	4/17/2016	4/24/2016	2	2	2	10	11	25	12	13	3	4	6	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-17	PRW2-125-3d	ESICEE	4/26/2016	5/3/2016	2	1	2	9	10	29	15	14	4	5	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-18	PRW2-125-3e	ESICEE	4/27/2016	5/4/2016	2	2	2	9	10	26	18	8	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-19	PRW2-SVE	ESICEE	5/31/2016	5/31/2016	1	2	1	5	15	50	21	29	4	6	11	Arduino	Scratch
Y1-20	PRIA-1-01	PRIA	2/8/2016	2/9/2016	2	1	3	13	20	91	76	15	2	9	17	Botball (Link Controller)	C/C++/Arduino
Y1-21	PRIA-1-02	PRIA	2/16/2016	4/12/2016	4	1	3	8	10	10	6	4	2	3	4	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y1-22	PRIA-1-03	PRIA	3/9/2016	4/14/2016	5	1	1	9	11	21	14	7	2	3	9	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y1-23	PRIA-1-04	PRIA	3/30/2016	3/31/2016	2	1	0	12	15	11	8	3	2	3	4	Botball (Link Controller)	C/C++/Arduino
Y1-24	PRIA-1-05	PRIA	6/1/2016	6/3/2016	3	1	1	8	11	21	12	9	3	3	7	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y1-25	PRIA-1-06	PRIA	6/2/2016	6/7/2016	3	1	0	6	8	23	10	13	10	11	2	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y1-26	PRIA-1-07	PRIA	6/5/2016	6/8/2016	2	1	1	9	11	24	13	11	2	3	9	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y1-27	PRIA-1-08	PRIA	6/10/2016	6/15/2016	3	1	0	10	12	21	10	11	10	11	2	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y1-28	PRIA-1-09	PRIA	6/13/2016	6/23/2016	2	1	1	8	10	22	11	11	2	3	9	LEGO Mindstorms and Botball	LEGO Mindstorms and C

ERW No	Code	Partner name	Dates from	Dates to	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other	Age of students	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male	Number of female	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
Y1-29	PRIA-1-10	PRIA	6/13/2016	6/23/2016	2	1	1	12	14	22	11	11	2	3	9	LEGO Mindstorms and Botball	LEGO Mindstorms and C
Y1-30	PRIA-1-11	PRIA	6/16/2016	6/17/2016	2	1	1	9	10	20	9	11	2	3	8	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y1-31	PRIA-1-12	PRIA	7/20/2016	7/20/2016	1	2	0	12	15	23	12	11	2	3	8	Botball (Link Controller)	C/C++/Arduino
Y1-32	PRIA-1-13	PRIA	6/21/2016	6/21/2016	1	2	0	12	14	23	11	12	2	3	10	Botball (Link Controller)	C/C++/Arduino
Y1-33	PRIA-1-14	PRIA	6/22/2016	6/22/2016	1	1	0	12	14	18	12	6	2	2	9	Botball (Link Controller)	C/C++/Arduino
Y1-34	PRIA-1-15	PRIA	6/27/2016	6/28/2016	2	1	0	12	13	14	14	0	2	2	7	Botball (Link Controller)	C/C++/Arduino
Y1-35	PRIA-1-16	PRIA	6/28/2016	6/29/2016	2	1	0	13	14	13	8	5	1	2	7	Botball (Link Controller)	C/C++/Arduino
Y1-36	TUW-20161	TUWien	6/1/2016	6/1/2016	1	1	2	14	15	19	8	11	2	3	8	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y1-37	TUW-20164	TUWien	6/8/2016	6/8/2016	1	1	2	13	14	20	6	14	2	3	9	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y1-38	TUW-20163	TUWien	6/9/2016	6/9/2016	1	1	2	13	14	18	12	6	2	3	8	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y1-39	TUW-20162	TUWien	6/15/2016	6/15/2016	1	1	2	14	16	22	10	12	2	3	10	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y1-40	TUW-20166	TUWien	6/16/2016	6/16/2016	1	1	2	13	14	21	3	18	2	3	8	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y1-41	TUW-20165	TUWien	6/23/2016	6/23/2016	1	1	2	14	16	24	7	17	2	3	10	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y1-42	UoA-413	UoA	3/8/2016	4/11/2016	6	0	0	14	16	65	32	33	2	4	22	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms

ERW No	Code	Partner name	Dates from	Dates to	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other	Age of students	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male	Number of female	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
Y1-43	UoA-414	UoA	3/15/2016	3/22/2016	2	0	0	13	14	12	6	6	3	3	4	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y1-44	UoA-415	UoA	4/6/2016	4/24/2016	6	0	0	10	12	34	16	18	3	4	10	LEGO WeDo	LEGO WeDo
Y1-45	UoA-416	UoA	4/6/2016	4/20/2016	3	0	0	15	15	25	13	12	4	5	6	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y1-46	UoA-417	UoA	4/7/2016	7/8/2016	2	0	0	16	18	19	12	7	3	4	6	Arduino	C/C++/Arduino
Y1-47	UoA-418	UoA	4/13/2016	4/21/2016	2	0	0	12	12	25	9	16	2	3	8	LEGO WeDo	LEGO WeDo
Y1-48	UoA-419	UoA	4/15/2016	4/22/2016	2	1	0	12	15	15	14	1	2	3	6	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-01	AL-2-2-CAT	AcrossLimits	3/27/2017	3/28/2017	2	2	1	10	13	23	9	14	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-02	AL-2-1-CAT	AcrossLimits	3/23/2017	3/24/2017	2	2	1	11	12	26	10	16	2	4	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-03	AL-2-3-CAT	AcrossLimits	3/29/2017	3/30/2017	2	2	0	12	13	27	8	19	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-04	AL-2-8-FRA	AcrossLimits	5/2/2017	5/4/2017	2	2	0	11	12	26	0	26	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-05	AL-2-9-FRA	AcrossLimits	5/5/2017	5/8/2017	2	2	0	11	12	24	0	24	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-06	AL-2-10-FRA	AcrossLimits	5/11/2017	5/12/2017	2	2	0	11	12	26	0	26	2	4	12	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-07	AL-2-6-JOS	AcrossLimits	4/25/2017	4/28/2017	2	2	0	11	13	23	0	23	2	3	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-08	AL-2-7-JOS	AcrossLimits	5/17/2017	5/18/2017	2	2	0	11	12	25	0	25	2	3	12	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-09	AL-2-4-VER	AcrossLimits	4/5/2017	4/6/2017	2	2	1	12	14	15	8	7	2	3	7	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-10	AL-2-2-VER	AcrossLimits	3/23/2017	3/24/2017	2	2	0	12	13	16	12	4	2	2	8	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals

ERW No	Code	Partner name	Dates from	Dates to	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other	Age of students	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male	Number of female	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
Y2-11	AL-1-13-StFrancesMsidaB	AcrossLimits	12/5/2016	12/6/2016	2	2	0	9	10	27	15	12	2	3	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-12	AL-1-8-AugustineA	AcrossLimits	10/24/2016	10/25/2016	2	2	0	9	10	24	24	0	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-13	AL-1-9-AugustineB	AcrossLimits	10/27/2016	10/28/2016	2	2	0	9	10	25	25	0	2	3	12	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-14	AL-1-7-DorothyA	AcrossLimits	10/17/2016	10/18/2016	2	2	1	9	11	25	0	25	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-15	AL-1-12-StFrancesMsidaA	AcrossLimits	11/28/2016	11/29/2016	2	2	0	9	11	26	13	13	2	3	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-16	AL-1-11-NicholasB	AcrossLimits	11/16/2016	11/17/2016	2	2	0	9	11	26	8	18	2	3	12	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-17	AL-1-10-NicholasA	AcrossLimits	11/14/2016	11/15/2016	2	2	0	9	10	23	16	7	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y2-18	PRIA-2-A3-02-AB	PRIA	10/3/2016	1/9/2017	2	1	0	13	14	16	14	2	1	3	15	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-19	PRIA-2-A3-03-AM	PRIA	12/5/2016	12/5/2016	1	1	1	14	16	19	11	8	2	3	7	Hedgehog	Python
Y2-20	PRIA-2-A3-01-ECERWS	PRIA	2/2/2017	2/3/2017	2	1	2	9	19	84	75	9	3	15	15	Botball: Wallaby controller	C/C++/Arduino
Y2-21	PRIA-2-A2-07-MG	PRIA	5/10/2017	5/15/2017	1	1	0	10	14	10	7	3	2	2	5	Hedgehog	Python
Y2-22	PRIA-2-A2-02-MG	PRIA	1/9/2017	1/23/2017	2	1	0	13	15	16	14	2	2	3	7	Hedgehog	Python
Y2-23	PRIA-2-A2-05-AS	PRIA	1/30/2017	1/30/2017	1	1	1	12	14	26	16	10	3	4	8	Hedgehog	Python
Y2-24	PRIA-2-A2-03-AM	PRIA	12/22/2016	12/22/2016	1	1	1	11	13	21	12	9	2	3	9	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-25	PRIA-2-A2-06-MA	PRIA	1/31/2017	1/31/2017	1	1	0	12	14	21	4	17	2	3	9	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms

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Y2-26	PRIA-2-A2-04-MA	PRIA	1/27/2017	1/27/2017	1	1	0	12	14	15	9	6	2	3	7	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-27	PRIA-2-A2-01-MG	PRIA	1/20/2017	1/27/2017	1	1	0	12	13	15	8	7	2	3	7	Hedgehog	Python
Y2-28	PRIA-2-A1-03-VA	PRIA	12/20/2016	12/21/2016	2	1	0	7	9	18	11	7	2	3	8	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-29	PRIA-2-A1-01-VA	PRIA	1/10/2017	1/13/2017	2	1	0	9	11	18	5	13	2	3	8	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-30	PRIA-2-A1-02-VV	PRIA	11/24/2016	12/1/2016	3	1	2	7	9	22	15	7	2	3	7	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-31	TU-Wien-2017-02-01	TUWien	2/1/2017	2/1/2017	2	1	2	13	14	23	6	17	2	12	9	LEGO WeDo	ASEBA
Y2-32	TU-Wien-2017-03-06	TUWien	3/6/2017	3/7/2017	2	1	2	6	10	24	14	10	2	11	10	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y2-33	TU-Wien-2017-06-13	TUWien	6/13/2017	6/13/2017	2	1	2	14	16	26	14	12	2	12	10	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y2-34	TU-Wien-2017-01-26	TUWien	1/25/2017	1/26/2017	1	1	2	6	7	24	9	15	2	13	10	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y2-35	TU-Wien-2017-03-30	TUWien	3/30/2017	3/30/2017	2	1	2	14	18	23	15	8	2	11	7	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y2-36	TU-Wien-2017-01-31	TUWien	1/30/2017	1/31/2017	2	1	2	6	7	23	12	11	2	12	8	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y2-37	TU-Wien-2017-02-02	TUWien	2/2/2017	2/2/2017	2	1	2	13	15	15	8	7	2	15	7	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y2-38	TU-Wien-2017-04-19	TUWien	4/19/2017	4/28/2017	2	1	2	9	11	20	9	11	2	10	9	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y2-39	TU-Wien-2017-02-23	TUWien	2/23/2017	3/2/2017	2	1	2	8	11	20	8	12	2	8	7	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y2-40	UoA421	UoA	5/18/2017	6/2/2017	4	1	0	10	11	22	10	12	3	4	6	LEGO WeDo	Scratch
Y2-41	UoA422	UoA	5/5/2017	5/24/2017	3	1	0	11	12	16	10	6	4	4	4	LEGO WeDo	LEGO WeDo
Y2-42	UoA423a	UoA	3/31/2017	5/8/2017	4	1	1	13	14	10	6	4	2	3	4	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms

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Y2-43	UoA423b	UoA	5/15/2017	5/26/2017	4	1	1	13	15	5	5	0	2	4	2	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-44	UoA424a	UoA	5/5/2017	5/24/2017	3	1	0	14	15	12	4	8	3	3	4	Arduino	C/C++/Arduino
Y2-45	UoA424b	UoA	5/5/2017	5/24/2017	2	1	0	14	15	15	10	5	3	3	5	Arduino	C/C++/Arduino
Y2-46	UoA425	UoA	3/20/2017	4/10/2017	2	1	0	12	15	15	14	1	2	3	5	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-47	UoA426	UoA	5/4/2017	5/8/2017	3	1	0	15	16	17	11	6	3	4	5	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-48	UoA427a	UoA	3/22/2017	3/29/2017	2	1	1	13	15	15	7	8	3	3	5	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-49	UoA427b	UoA	5/2/2017	5/9/2017	2	1	1	13	15	15	9	6	3	3	5	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y2-50	PRW2-2-125-4v	ESICEE	11/21/2016	11/28/2016	2	2	1	9	11	30	14	16	3	5	7	Finch	Scratch
Y2-51	PRW2-2-125-4g	ESICEE	11/24/2016	12/1/2016	2	2	1	9	11	27	15	12	1	5	7	Finch	Scratch
Y2-52	PRW2-2-125-4e	ESICEE	11/25/2016	12/2/2016	2	2	1	9	10	30	21	9	2	5	7	Finch	Scratch
Y2-53	PRW2-2-125-4d	ESICEE	11/11/2016	11/18/2016	2	2	1	9	10	29	14	15	2	5	7	Finch	Scratch
Y2-54	PRW2-2-125-4b	ESICEE	11/22/2016	11/29/2016	2	2	1	9	11	26	12	14	3	4	7	Finch	Scratch
Y2-55	PRW2-2-125-4a	ESICEE	11/10/2016	11/17/2016	2	2	1	9	11	28	17	11	3	5	7	Finch	Scratch
Y2-56	PRW2-2-125-3V	ESICEE	10/6/2016	10/10/2016	2	3	1	8	10	26	15	11	3	5	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y2-57	PRW2-2-125-3G	ESICEE	7/10/2016	12/10/2016	2	3	1	8	9	28	15	13	3	5	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y2-58	PRW2-2-125-3E	ESICEE	5/12/2016	12/12/2016	2	3	2	9	9	27	15	12	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y2-59	PRW2-2-125-3D	ESICEE	10/24/2016	12/13/2016	2	3	1	8	10	27	13	14	2	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y2-60	PRW2-2-125-3b	ESICEE	10/4/2016	10/10/2016	2	2	1	8	9	26	13	13	3	5	6	Arduino	Scratch

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Y2-61	PRW2-2-125-3a	ESICEE	10/3/2016	10/11/2016	2	3	1	8	9	25	12	13	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y2-62	PRW2-2-125-6e	ESICEE	10/19/2016	12/6/2016	3	3	1	11	12	25	16	9	2	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y2-63	PRW2-2-125-Kyustendil	ESICEE	12/5/2016	12/5/2016	1	2	2	11	12	21	15	6	4	7	4	Arduino	Scratch
Y2-64	621_NWETSS_1	CU	5/5/2017	5/29/2017	4	1	1	13	14	15	7	8	1	2	19	Slurtles	Scratch
Y2-65	621_NWETSS_2	CU	5/5/2017	5/29/2017	4	1	1	12	14	17	10	7	1	2	17	Slurtles	Scratch
Y2-66	622_MIHS_1	CU	3/7/2017	4/6/2017	6	1	1	11	12	21	9	12	1	2	21	Slurtles	Scratch
Y2-67	622_MIHA_2	CU	7/2/2017	6/8/2017	6	1	1	11	12	22	10	12	1	3	11	Slurtles	Scratch
Y2-68	625_OFPS_1	CU	3/17/2017	4/30/2017	5	1	0	8	10	19	5	14	1	3	9	Slurtles	Scratch
Y2-69	622_MIHA_3	CU	6/20/2017	6/18/2017	5	1	1	11	12	24	11	13	1	4	11	Slurtles	Scratch
Y2-70	624_CA_1	CU	3/20/2017	4/3/2017	3	2	1	9	11	29	18	11	2	4	13	Micro:bit; Raspberry Pi, electronics, Felt and sewing kit	Block in Micro:bits
Y3-01	AL-2-11-VER3	AcrossLimits	9/6/2017	9/7/2017	2	2	1	11	13	19	12	7	2	3	0	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-02	AL-2-12-VER4	AcrossLimits	9/12/2017	9/13/2017	2	2	1	11	12	20	10	10	2	2	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-03	AL-2-13-StCat	AcrossLimits	10/9/2017	10/10/2017	2	2	0	10	12	23	10	13	2	3	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-04	AL-2-14-StCat	AcrossLimits	10/16/2017	10/17/2017	2	2	0	10	12	23	9	14	2	3	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-05	AL-3-7-QSI-Class1	AcrossLimits	6/5/2018	6/5/2018	1	2	0	9	10	11	7	4	2	3	5	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals

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Y3-06	AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors	AcrossLimits	5/14/2018	5/14/2018	1	2	0	9	10	25	0	25	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-07	AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2	AcrossLimits	5/26/2018	5/26/2018	1	2	0	9	12	12	9	3	2	2	3	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-08	AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1	AcrossLimits	5/29/2018	5/29/2018	1	2	0	9	10	25	0	25	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-09	AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1	AcrossLimits	5/31/2018	5/31/2018	1	2	1	8	9	24	0	24	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-10	AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors	AcrossLimits	5/15/2018	5/15/2018	1	2	0	9	10	26	0	26	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-11	AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1	AcrossLimits	6/4/2018	6/4/2018	1	3	0	10	12	25	0	25	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-12	AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1	AcrossLimits	5/28/2018	5/28/2018	1	2	0	6	7	13	5	8	2	3	6	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-13	AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3	AcrossLimits	5/30/2018	5/30/2018	1	2	0	6	7	23	13	10	2	4	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
Y3-14	PRW2-3-125-3a	ESICEE	2/20/2018	2/27/2018	2	2	1	9	10	27	9	18	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y3-15	PRW2-3-125-3b	ESICEE	3/7/2018	3/12/2018	2	2	0	9	10	24	15	9	3	4	6	Arduino	Scratch
Y3-16	PRW2-3-125-3d	ESICEE	3/20/2018	3/27/2018	2	2	0	9	10	28	15	13	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y3-17	PRW2-3-125-3e	ESICEE	3/19/2018	3/26/2018	2	2	0	8	10	28	13	15	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y3-18	PRW2-3-125-3g	ESICEE	2/27/2018	3/6/2018	2	1	0	8	10	26	11	15	2	4	6	Arduino	Scratch

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Y3-19	PRW2-3-125-3v	ESICEE	2/20/2018	2/27/2018	2	1	1	9	10	28	13	15	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
Y3-20	PRW2-3-125-4a	ESICEE	10/2/2017	10/9/2017	2	1	2	9	10	26	13	13	2	4	7	Finch	Scratch
Y3-21	PRW2-3-125-4b	ESICEE	10/3/2017	10/10/2017	2	2	3	9	10	28	13	15	2	4	7	Finch	Scratch
Y3-22	PRW2-3-125-4d	ESICEE	11/13/2017	11/20/2017	2	1	0	9	11	27	13	14	3	4	7	Finch	Scratch
Y3-23	PRW2-3-125-4e	ESICEE	11/14/2017	11/21/2017	2	1	0	9	10	26	15	11	2	5	6	Finch	Scratch
Y3-24	PRW2-3-125-4g	ESICEE	10/17/2017	10/24/2017	2	1	1	9	10	28	16	12	4	4	7	Finch	Scratch
Y3-25	PRW2-3-125-4v	ESICEE	10/16/2017	10/23/2017	2	1	1	9	10	26	16	10	3	5	6	Finch	Scratch
Y3-26	PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm	ESICEE	4/23/2018	4/30/2018	2	1	0	10	12	27	22	5	2	5	7	Robotic Arm Kit - CBIS Education	Scratch
Y3-27	PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm	ESICEE	5/24/2018	5/28/2018	2	1	0	11	12	27	20	7	3	5	7	Robotic Arm Kit - CBIS Education	Scratch
Y3-28	PRW2-3-Kuystendil	ESICEE	5/18/2018	5/18/2018	1	1	0	10	12	20	13	7	4	4	5	Robotic Arm Kit - CBIS Education	Scratch
Y3-29	PRIA-3-A2-03-MG	PRIA	10/20/2017	1/8/2018	3	1	0	12	15	24	14	10	2	4	9	Hedgehog	Python
Y3-30	PRIA-3-A2-02-MG	PRIA	10/19/2017	1/15/2018	3	1	0	12	15	22	12	10	1	3	10	Hedgehog	Python
Y3-31	PRIA-3-A1-03-VA	PRIA	11/7/2017	1/29/2018	3	1	2	7	10	21	14	7	1	3	10	Hedgehog	Python
Y3-32	PRIA-3-A2-01-AB	PRIA	10/9/2017	1/15/2018	8	1	2	13	14	18	17	1	1	6	11	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y3-33	PRIA-3-A2-04-MA	PRIA	11/16/2017	2/1/2018	3	1	2	10	13	26	8	18	2	5	7	Hedgehog	Python

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Y3-34	PRIA-3-A1-04-VA	PRIA	11/9/2017	4/9/2018	2	1	2	8	11	21	13	8	1	3	0	Hedgehog	Blockly
Y3-35	PRIA-3-A2-05-MA	PRIA	11/16/2017	2/1/2018	3	1	2	11	14	25	5	20	2	4	10	Hedgehog	Python
Y3-36	PRIA-3-A1-05-KL	PRIA	4/23/2018	5/7/2018	2	1	2	8	10	25	11	14	2	3	10	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y3-37	PRIA-3-A1-02-VV	PRIA	10/5/2017	2/26/2018	3	1	2	8	10	28	12	16	2	3	12	Hedgehog	Blockly
Y3-38	PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS	PRIA	1/22/2018	1/23/2018	2	1	2	13	18	55	48	7	2	9	10	Botball: Wallaby controller	C/C++/Arduino
Y3-39	PRIA-3-A1-01-VV	PRIA	9/28/2017	1/26/2018	3	2	3	8	11	18	12	6	1	3	9	Hedgehog	Blockly
Y3-40	TU_RoboticClub_2018	TUWien	2/26/2018	5/28/2018	10	0	0	6	11	10	6	4	1	2	6	Thymio II	ASEBA
Y3-41	TUW_050318_Workshop_20180305	TUWien	3/5/2018	3/12/2018	2	1	0	18	18	13	13	0	2	3	5	Thymio II	Blockly
Y3-42	TUW_060418_Workshop_20180406	TUWien	4/6/2018	4/13/2018	2	1	0	9	12	18	8	10	2	3	9	Thymio II	Thymio VPL
Y3-43	TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410	TUWien	4/10/2018	4/24/2018	3	2	0	14	18	25	14	11	2	5	9	Thymio II	Thymio VPL
Y3-44	TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411	TUWien	4/11/2018	4/25/2018	3	3	0	14	16	28	16	12	2	5	10	Thymio II	Thymio VPL
Y3-45	TUW_140218_Workshop_20180214	TUWien	2/14/2018	2/15/2018	2	1	0	7	9	25	13	12	2	4	9	Thymio II	Blockly

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Y3-46	TUW_140318_Workshop_20180314	TUWien	3/14/2018	3/15/2018	2	1	0	8	9	23	11	12	2	4	10	Thymio II	Blockly
Y3-47	TUW_190318_Workshop_20180319	TUWien	3/19/2018	3/23/2018	2	1	0	8	9	19	12	7	2	3	9	Thymio II	Blockly
Y3-48	TUW_220218_Workshop_20180222	TUWien	2/22/2018	2/23/2018	2	1	0	7	9	25	10	15	2	4	10	Thymio II	Blockly
Y3-49	TUW_250418_Workshop_20180425	TUWien	4/25/2018	4/26/2018	2	1	0	6	10	22	10	12	2	4	10	Thymio II	Thymio VPL
Y3-50	TUWien-ITA-2017	TUWien	12/22/2017	12/22/2017	1	1	1	14	15	24	13	11	1	3	10	Thymio II	Text programming
Y3-51	631_MIHS_1	CU	9/11/2017	10/24/2017	6	2	1	13	14	23	14	9	1	3	0	SLurtle	Scratch
Y3-52	631_MIHS_1b	CU	11/6/2017	12/12/2017	6	3	2	13	14	23	14	9	1	3	0	SLurtle	Scratch
Y3-53	631_MIHS_2	CU	1/15/2018	2/6/2018	6	4	3	13	14	29	15	14	1	2	15	SLurtle	Scratch
Y3-54	631_MIHS_2b	CU	2/19/2018	3/26/2018	6	5	4	13	14	29	15	14	1	2	0	SLurtle	Scratch
Y3-55	631_MIHS_3	CU	4/23/2018	5/22/2018	6	6	5	13	14	32	17	15	0	0	0	Slurtles	ICT/CS
Y3-56	631_MIHS_3b	CU	6/4/2018	7/10/2018	6	7	6	13	14	32	17	15	0	0	0	Slurtles	ICT/CS
Y3-57	632_MIHS_1	CU	9/11/2017	10/24/2017	6	8	7	13	14	22	9	13	2	2	0	SLurtle	Scratch
Y3-58	632_MIHS_1b	CU	11/6/2017	12/12/2017	6	9	8	13	14	22	9	13	2	2	0	SLurtle	Scratch
Y3-59	632_MIHS_2	CU	1/15/2018	2/6/2018	6	10	9	13	14	24	10	14	0	0	0	SLurtle	Scratch
Y3-60	632_MIHS_2b	CU	2/11/2018	3/26/2018	6	11	10	13	14	24	10	14	0	0	0	SLurtle	Scratch

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Y3-61	633_PYD_1	CU	11/16/2017	12/14/2017	3	12	11	13	14	29	15	14	1	1	27	Slurtles	Scratch
Y3-62	632_MIHS_3	CU	4/23/2018	5/22/2018	6	11	10	13	14	31	17	14	0	0	0	Slurtles	ICT/CS
Y3-63	632_MIHS_3b	CU	6/4/2018	7/10/2018	6	12	11	13	14	31	17	14	0	0	0	Slurtles	ICT/CS
Y3-64	UoA 437	UoA	2/27/2018	3/1/2018	3	3	1	16	17	11	11	0	2	5	3	Arduino	C/C++/Arduino
Y3-65	UoA 434b	UoA	3/13/2018	4/17/2018	4	4	2	14	17	15	11	4	1	3	5	Arduino	C/C++/Arduino
Y3-66	UoA 434a	UoA	2/1/2018	3/8/2018	5	5	3	14	15	15	7	8	1	3	5	Arduino	C/C++/Arduino
Y3-67	UoA 432	UoA	12/18/2017	12/22/2017	3	6	4	11	11	18	10	8	4	5	4	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y3-68	UoA 431	UoA	3/15/2018	3/30/2018	3	7	5	10	10	13	6	7	1	5	4	LEGO WeDo	Scratch
Y3-69	UoA 438	UoA	12/16/2017	12/17/2017	3	8	6	11	15	21	12	9	0	0	0	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y3-70	UoA 436	UoA	4/25/2018	5/22/2018	4	9	7	10	11	22	11	11	3	4	6	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y3-71	UoA 435	UoA	2/19/2018	3/2/2018	3	10	8	6	13	13	12	1	2	3	5	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
Y3-72	UoA 433	UoA	1/27/2018	2/10/2018	3	11	9	10	15	17	10	7	2	4	5	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms

